

VHEMBE BIOSPHERE RESERVE PERIODIC REVIEW 2009-2019

Acknowledgements

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Finally, the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve is testament to Dr Ian Gaigher's (26.10.1943 – 08.04.2020) abiding legacy of Conservation in Southern Africa. This submission is dedicated to him.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AfriMAB	African Network of Biosphere Reserves
BDP	Biosphere Demonstration Project
BLM	Blouberg Local Municipality
CDM	Capricorn District Municipality
CBA	Critical Biodiversity Area
CBD	Convention of Biological Diversity
CPPP's	Community/Public/Private Partnerships
DEFF	Department of Environment, Forestry and Fisheries
DLM	Dzumo la Mupo Foundation
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EMF	Environmental Management Framework
EWT	Endangered Wildlife Trust
GEF	Global Environmental Facility
GIS	Geographic Information System
GLTFCA	Great Limpopo Transfrontier Conservation Area
GMTFCA	Greater Mapungubwe Transfrontier Conservation Area
IDP	Integrated Development Plan
KNP	Kruger National Park
K2CBR	Kruger to Canyon Biosphere Reserve
LEDET	Limpopo Economic Development, Environment and Tourism
LCP	Limpopo Conservation Plan (Version 2, 2013)
MAB	Man and the Biosphere Programme
MNP	Mapungubwe National Park
MoA	Memorandum of Agreement
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NEMPAA	National Environmental Management: Protected Areas Act
NPAES	National Protection Areas Expansion Strategy
NPC	Non-Profit Company
NR	Nature Reserve

NSBA	National Spatial Biodiversity Assessment
RAMSAR	RAMSAR Convention on Wetlands
SARChI	The South African Research Chairs Initiative
SANBI	South African National Biodiversity Institute
SANParks	South African National Parks
SEF	Strategic Environmental Focus
SEMP	Strategic Environmental Management Plan
SDF	Spatial Development Framework
SEZ	Special Economic Zone
SGP	Small Grant Program
TFCA	Transfrontier Conservation Areas
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
VDM	Vhembe District Municipality
WBR	Waterberg Biosphere Reserve

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PART I: SUMMARY

1 INTRODUCTION

The Vhembe Biosphere Reserve (VBR) is located in the most northern districts of the Limpopo Province of the Republic of South Africa (hereinafter referred to as South Africa; Figure 2), and includes the northern Kruger National Park north of the Shingwedzi River, and borders the three neighbouring countries of Botswana, Zimbabwe and Mozambique. The VBR is the second largest biosphere reserve in South Africa, with a surface area of 30 700 km². With a population of approximately 1.5 million people of which ~97% are rural residents, the VBR contains a complex interplay of cultural groups representing a rich, but diverse, cultural heritage. These groups exist within a socio-political post-apartheid-regime in an area of the country with extraordinary biodiversity and several sensitive eco-systems. The biosphere reserve was designated in 2009 by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) and this is the first periodic review spanning the 10 years from 2009 to 2019.

Figure 2: A map showing the location of the VBR in Africa (marked in red) in the top north of South Africa. Inset shows detail of the VBR.

Implementation-measures to achieve VBR objectives

Except for conservation- related projects, the VBR Non-Profit Company (VBR NPC) facilitated, rather than implemented projects. The VBR works with implementation organisations to achieve objectives according to the UNESCO Man and the Biosphere Programme (MAB). This was determined by the VBR as the most cost-effective way to operate due to limitations with resources and led to constructive collaboration and integration of functions across disciplines and organisations.

This Review focuses on the projects incorporated by the VBR since 2009 and highlights the roles various institutions have played during this period. It is the culmination of twenty years of dedicated, voluntary work by the VBR Steering Committee, established 10 years before nomination, and the VBR NPC Board and its task teams, representing the past 10 years after nomination.

A major achievement arising from the establishment of the VBR, was the award by the Department of Science and Innovation and the National Research Foundation (NRF) of a South African Research Chair (SARChi) to the University of Venda (UNIVEN); this was for '*Biodiversity Value and Change in the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve*', and focuses substantially on research and monitoring. The main purpose of the SARChi is to improve the quality and quantity of tertiary education (e.g. supporting 20 Honours, 20 MSc and 10 PhD theses in conservation biology in the Biosphere between 2014 and 2019) and to create awareness of the local and global importance and benefits of biosphere reserves amongst local communities and youth in the VBR.

Fulfilment of the VBR's conservation, development and logistic functions culminated in two significant studies that contributed to the achievements of the VBR's objectives. Undertaken by the VBR Conservation Task Team in 2016, a study to revise the zonation of the VBR¹ was completed in January 2019 (Appendix C). A consecutive study in 2016 (that incorporated the previous study), was commissioned by the VBR IPC to consultants Strategic Environmental Focus (Pty) Ltd to develop a Strategic Environmental Management Plan (SEMP)² (Appendix D). A summary of both these reports are detailed below:

a) Proposed Biodiversity Conservation Strategy for the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve zonation.

This has incorporated the provincial government's Limpopo Conservation plan (2013) which models critical biodiversity and ecological support areas on a coarse scale and assesses protection levels of the various habitats. The technical report, map and spatial files can be accessed by

¹ A Biodiversity Conservation Strategy for the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve

² Vhembe Biosphere Reserve Initial Strategic Environmental Management Plan : Desired State of the Environment Report with Environmental Management Guidelines

registering on the SANBI Biodiversity GIS website at <http://bgis.sanbi.org/>. Findings from the report indicated that protected areas in Limpopo need to be increased by an additional 85% over and above the current network. A conservation expansion strategy for each of the 25 ecosystem types has been proposed, based on the South African National Biodiversity Institute's (SANBI) conservation targets. This includes new and extended core conservation areas, situated largely within Critical Biodiversity Areas including all the current core conservation areas. All the present transformed areas are included in the transitional zone and the strategy proposes new buffer zones for areas situated between the core and transitional zones.

b) The VBR Initial Strategic Environmental Management Plan (SEMP): Desired State of the Environment Report with Environmental Management Guidelines (SEF, 2016)

Referred to as the Interim SEMP, these guidelines contain a summary of the technical work of our Conservation Task Team and other VBR committees during the past 10 years. It proposes a long-term strategy with management guidelines for conservation, development and land use in the VBR. An executive summary of the Initial SEMP representing the period 2009-2019, is in preparation as an accessible Report to relevant stakeholders. (Appendix L). Upon finalisation, the summary will be distributed to stakeholder groups.

Process of conducting the Periodic review

The Periodic Review was undertaken by a sub-committee of the VBR's Board of Directors with key members of its task teams; technical assistance was provided by the Department of Environment, Forestry Fisheries and Environment (DEFF). It has been developed through an extensive consultative, participatory and collaborative process with key role-players and stakeholders. Archived VBR documents including those of the Biosphere Reserve National Committee and VBR Board meeting reports were also reviewed.

VBR area and spatial configuration

The VBR is landlocked and its zones have not changed since its nomination by UNESCO in 2009 (Table 1). It covers 30 700 km² of which the Core Areas comprise 4 600 km², the Buffer Zones 3 574 km² and the Transition Areas 22 526 km².

Table 1: The configuration of the VBR since nomination by UNESCO in 2009. Please note that the zones represent both seasonal and permanent.

Terrestrial zones in the VBR	Area (km ²)	Changes in the 10 years (2009-2019)
Core	4 600	No change

Buffer	3574		
Transition	22 526		

1.4 Human population of the VBR

The Vhembe District Municipality (VDM) and the Blouberg Local Municipality (BLM) (within the Capricorn District Municipality (CDM)) together form the boundaries of the VBR. A census in the country revealed that the VBR had a total population of 1.36 million people in 2005 and are accepted as the figures when the VBR was nominated in 2009 (Table 2).

This increased to 1.5 million in 2011, whilst estimates in 2016 (National Government's Demographic Information) state the population is 1.554 million (Table 2).

Table 2 : Human population estimates in the VBR since 2005. Please note that the zones represent both seasonal and permanent.

Terrestrial zones in the VBR	National Census Figures (2005)	National Census Figures (2011)
Core	<2 000	2 500
Buffer	<5 000	5 500
Transition	~1.3 million	~1.5 million
Total	~1 307 000	~1 508 000

1.5 Budget and initiatives

The VBR budget (2009-2019) comprised of funding from the provincial government, which is LEDET. (This budget was not always sufficient to support VBR operational costs.)

LEDET provided funds for the operations of the VBR with an annual tranche of ~ R150 000 per annum which has been incremental per financial year. These funds were distributed from LEDET via the VDM with whom they have a Memorandum of Agreement to coordinate and manage the VBR. In return, the VBR has a Memorandum of Understanding with the VDM. In June 2019, LEDET implemented a mechanism whereby funds are transferred directly to the VBR which improved implementation of programs (Table 3).

Table 3 : The VBR budget (2009/10 vs 2019)

Budget at nomination (2009 -2010)	Budget (2019-2020)
No funding	R250 000 (for VBR operations)

The VBR provided financial assistance to various Biosphere Demonstration Projects namely; 1) Nombhela Nursery, 2) Adopt a River Project, 3) Baobab Foundation 4) Basani Waste 5) world Parks world Cup 6) Blouberg Bridge site restoration. Each Demonstration Project was allocated money, for the purchase of equipment.

Figure 3: Left: Thulamela archaeological site in the Makuleke concession area at Pafuri (northern Kruger National Park). Right: traditionally open-fired clay pots at Mukondeni,

Figure 4: Mapungubwe Hill (Mapungubwe National Park) surrounded by the arid, stark beauty of the Bosveld with strings of Baobabs

1.6 Framework of cooperation

The VBR collaborates with various national and international conservation programmes within the biosphere, such as the World Heritage Site, Transfrontier Conservation Areas (TFCA), the Greater Kruger Strategic Development Programme (Supported by the United Nations Development Programme), Ramsar Sites, South African National Parks, Endangered Wildlife Trust and Stewardship Programmes. As a result, the VBR contributes directly to the following international agreements and conventions:

- Convention on Biological Diversity;
- World Heritage Convention; and,
- African Network of Biosphere Reserves and the World Network of Biosphere Reserves.

Figure 5: San rock art at Makgabeng

All biosphere reserves in South Africa are recognised under the National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan for 2015 to 2025, as one of the programmes which assist in the implementation of the Convention on Biological Diversity's (CBD) Strategic Plan for 2011 to 2020. The VBR contributes to the implementation of this Strategic Plan, particularly the AICHI Biodiversity Targets. Examples are provided below:

- a) **World Heritage Convention:** Mapungubwe National Park (MNP; South African National Parks; SANParks) is a World Heritage Site situated in one of the Core zones of the VBR, whilst the Buffer zone of MNP forms part of the Buffer zone of the VBR. The VBR participates in the World Heritage Site Management through conservation management committees. The integrated management of the zones is critical as it affects both the World Heritage Site and the VBR.
- b) **Linkages with other Biosphere Reserves:** The VBR adheres to the UNESCO regulations for biosphere reserves and has several projects which cater for the development, conservation and logistic functions of the biosphere reserve. The VBR interacts with the Kruger to Canyon Biosphere Reserve (K2CBR) and Waterberg Biosphere Reserve (WBR) through attending the Limpopo Biosphere Reserves Forum; interaction with national biosphere reserves is achieved through the national committee. The VBR is physically connected with the K2CBR through the Greater Mapungubwe (GMTFCA) and the Great Limpopo Transfrontier Conservation Area (GLTFCA) corridors; VBR and K2CBR Buffer zones are both within Kruger National Park, and engagement regarding this Buffer zone is undertaken with SANParks.
- c) **The World Network of Biosphere Reserves (WNBR) and the African Network of Biosphere Reserves (AfrimAB):** LEDET organises regular forums for the three Limpopo biospheres with annual forums organised by MAB for all of South Africa's biospheres to meet. The VBR regularly

participates in AfriMAB meetings and workshops and implements its recommendations where relevant. The vice-chairperson of the VBR was part of the workshop that prepared the Management Manual for UNESCO Biosphere Reserves in Africa in 2015.

d) Transfrontier Conservation Area: The VBR falls within the Greater Mapungubwe (initiative between South Africa, Botswana and Zimbabwe) and also Great Limpopo Transfrontier Conservation Areas which is initiative involving South Africa, Mozambique, Zimbabwe. Termed as 'Smart Biosphere Reserves', the VBR serves as a learning platform for other biosphere reserves through the exchange of knowledge and information. In July 2013, the VBR and WBR hosted the AfriMAB capacity building workshop, with representatives from UNESCO and other African biosphere reserves.

Figure 6: Left: Mapungubwe Hill, middle: Samango monkey. Right: view from Lajuma (1 748 m A.S.L - the highest point in the Soutpansberg Mountains).

Figure 7: Left: Our beautiful indigenous Agaphantus. Right: Mopani worm, a source of protein in large areas of the VBR and Southern Africa

PART II: PERIODIC REVIEW REPORT

1 BIOSPHERE RESERVE - INTRODUCTION TO THE PROCESS OF THE REVIEW

This is the first Periodic Review undertaken for the VBR for the period 2009 to 2019. The process by which this 10-Year Periodic Review has been conducted involved consultation amongst the VBR Board and key members of the VBR's task-teams for Conservation, Development, Research and Education.

Relevant stakeholders (including the VDM, BLM, CDM, LEDET, DEFF, UNIVEN, the Endangered Wildlife Trust, SANPARKS, SANBI, NGOs, Traditional leadership, local communities representatives, Department of Agriculture, Office of the Premier of Limpopo) were also consulted and served as major role players during the process. Broad and extensive stakeholder engagement was obtained during the two Annual General Meetings (AGM) held prior to the registration of the VBR as an NPC. Subsequent stakeholder engagement-meetings were coordinated by the VBR with key institutions within the area.

Figure 8: Left: indigenous rainforest in the Soutpansberg. Middle: abundant birdlife to protect. Right: The Endangered Pangolin can still be found in the VBR

2 SIGNIFICANT CHANGES IN THE CONTEXT OF THE VBR

2.1 Significant changes during the past ten years

CHANGES IN THE LOCAL ECONOMY

From approximately 1.5 million residents in the VBR, 38.7% of these were unemployed in 2011, with youth unemployment rate, 50.6% at the time. This has created an increased dependence on social grants with concomitant social problems. A further effect is the increased amount of people moving to urban centres and the resulting 'brain-drain' of the region. The rural areas are therefore left with a combination of older people and a large young population, a situation aggravated by the low standard of education in 90% of the extremely ill-resourced rural schools.

The main economic activities in the VBR are mining, agriculture, tourism and commercial activities (Shopping malls) and these create the most employment.

To address the lack of employment opportunities, the South African government has proposed establishing a [Special Economic Zone \(SEZ\) in the VBR](#) with four projects envisioned in the Musina-Makhado area. These are 1) a coal-powered power-plant, 2) a coking plant, 3) an alloy factory and, 4) a steel manufacturer. While the VBR recognise that these developments may bring an improvement to the local economy, the impact on biodiversity within the VBR, is of major concern.

A positive development was the erection of the 28MW Soutpan Solar Power plant in the VBR. This is situated 72 km west of Louis Trichardt, close to the small farming town of Vivo, and generates approximately 61 000 megawatt hours per year. This provides sufficient clean, renewable electrical energy to power more than 13 000 average South African homes. The project is one of the first solar facilities arising from the South African Government's Renewable Energy Independent Power Producer Procurement Programme (REIPPPP). It covers 180 hectares of BDM-owned land in the VBR and generates electricity using 108 000 solar (PV) panels, which feed the 22 kilo Volt (kV) Eskom distribution system.

CHANGES IN LANDSCAPES AND HABITAT USE

Upon initiation of the VBR in 2009, the focus for conservation was primarily the national parks and provincial nature reserves. The VBR have worked with numerous stakeholders since 2009 to develop knowledge and stimulate a common vision for sustainable development, and expansion of conservation initiatives beyond the protected areas. The VBR works with numerous stakeholders to promote connectivity between various conservation areas i.e. National Parks, Provincial Nature Reserves and Key Biodiversity Areas. The VBR complement the Transfrontier Conservation Areas. Rural communities embraced the concept of the VBR and are also important drivers in the process.

Conservation of large carnivores through conflict mitigation, the impacts of climate change, development of local expertise in biodiversity assessment and conservation and the development of a common vision on sustainable development in the region have all been recognised as additional ways in which to conserve biodiversity.

People, from all levels of society, are starting to recognise that conserving biodiversity can improve their quality of life. For example, one rural community in the VBR petitioned against unsustainable development at their sacred and biologically sensitive area at the Phiphidi Waterfalls in the Eastern Soutpansberg whilst several local communities in the Limpopo River Valley lobbied against mining in their water-restricted environment.

Figure 9: Left: Southern African Python, middle: Makgabeng. Right: Chacma baboon

Figure 10: Left: Rock paintings at Makgabeng. Right: Baobab in the Limpopo River Valley

Discussions are currently underway with community leaders to expand important conservation areas in the Makgabeng, Blouberg and eastern Soutpansberg too. The existence of the VBR was an important motivation for the establishment of the Chair in Biodiversity Change and Conservation at UNIVEN under the South African Research Chairs Initiative (SARChI). This Chair contributed significantly to the development of local expertise (especially amongst the youth), as well as attracting scientists and research support from different parts of the world. This scientific input provided valuable information and support for aspects related to sustainable farming, negative impacts of climate change and problem-animal mitigation. The Chair also formed an important hub for the processing of information by scientists working in the region.

The VBR's Conservation Task Team, together with the EWT, initiated a public participation process with landowners that led to the establishment of new legally conserved areas. This was achieved through the Stewardship Programme in biodiversity hotspots that were previously poorly conserved and includes the Luvhondo Nature Reserve in the Western Soutpansberg, as well as in the Sandveld area north of the Soutpansberg and the farming area north of the Nwanedi Nature Reserve. There have also been government initiatives like the Makuya Park co management agreements which seeks to facilitate the involvement of the local people in conservation and beneficiation of local people.

The Conservation Task Team together with SANParks and NGOs are also currently assisting landowners to create large conservation landscapes in the Limpopo River Valley. These will link to the GMTFCA and, if successful, will be one of the most significant conservation developments in southern Africa in the last 50 years and could contribute significantly to sustainable job-creation. There have also been government initiatives like the Makuya park (co management agreement) which seeks to facilitate the involvement of the local people in conservation and beneficiation of local people.

Figure 11: Left: Leopards are still a regular sight in the VBR. Right: the work of Justice Mugwena, one of many master crafters in the VBR, still keeping indigenous traditions and skills alive

CHANGES IN GOVERNANCE

The biggest change following nomination in 2009 was that the initial VBR Stakeholder's Council registered a Non-Profit Company (NPC) with a Board of Directors to govern the VBR. Prior to this, the VBR acted as an NGO. In a public AGM in Thohoyandou in 2016, a new Board of Directors was elected and the current board of directors was elected in February of 2020

CHANGES IN MANAGEMENT

The work of the Board of Directors and its task teams has been 100% voluntary, except for a nominal amount paid monthly to an acting coordinator (between March 2017 and April 2018) and a nominal amount paid to a part-time acting coordinator (pre-2015). From 2019 the VBR appointed a full time Coordinator who is now responsible for the day to day running of the activities. The current board of directors consist of 8 members: Chairperson, Deputy Chairperson, Secretary, Deputy Secretary, Treasurer and 3 additional members. At the recently held AGM it was agreed that at least one of the board members should be reserved for youth (18-30years)

Figure 12: Subsistence farming in Venda. It is normally the women in the family who undertake this work (during raining season in the summer)

2.2 Brief updated background information

VBR BOUNDARY COORDINATES

The coordinates for the VBR remain unchanged since 2009, with the coordinates of the central point being: 22.794241° S, 30.002458° E.

Table 4: The bounding coordinates of the VBR (as of 2009)

Corner	Coordinate
West	28.658944° E
East	31.563712° E
North	22.125786° S
South	23.570540° S

Figure 14: The VBR in relation to the five local municipal areas: Makhado, Blouberg, Musina, Mutale and Thulamela and the northern Kruger National Park in the east. Note that only Blouberg Local Municipality falls under the Capricorn District Municipality, the rest fall under the Vhembe District Municipality

UPDATE ON CONSERVATION

The nomination application in 2009, proposed that the existing proclaimed provincial nature reserves and national parks form the Core Areas of the VBR, whilst the Buffer Zones constitute the availability of relatively undisturbed adjoining areas.

Table 5: METT-SA Performance of State Owned Nature Reserves (SONR)

Name	2016	2017	2018
1. Makuya Nature Reserve.	36%	42%	42%
2. Mphaphuli Nature Reserve.	24%	-	45%
3. Musina Nature Reserve.	39%	49%	56%
4. Brackenridge Nature Reserve.	24%	28%	28%
5. Langjan Nature Reserve.	33%	57%	36%
6. Nwanedi Nature Reserve.	35%	43%	58%
7. Nzhelele Nature Reserve.	36%	48%	50%

There has been an improved performance of SONR over the years, these reserves are key to biodiversity conservation and management in the VBR (Mmphidi, 2019).

Although the existing Core Areas are important for biodiversity conservation, the VBR's research during the past ten years indicates that a lot still need to be done to ensure the core areas provide sustainable conservation of ecosystems, threatened species or ecosystem services. Therefore, a critical element in the Conservation Task Team's recommendations, is the proposed connectivity of the Core Areas by corridors.

The current zonation of the VBR, has not changed. The Conservation Task Team has recently recommended a revised zonation and a new Biodiversity Conservation Strategy as can be seen in Appendix C.

The Biodiversity Conservation Strategy is largely based on biodiversity assessments and workshops with local and international experts over the past eight years, like the Limpopo Conservation Plan (Desmet et al. 2013) and Vhembe District Bioregional Plan (LEDET 2017)

UPDATE ON DEVELOPMENT

The VBR NPC cooperates with implementation organisations to support many sustainable development initiatives in the VBR. To assist management, the VBR's borders were intentionally delineated to fall within the VDM and BLM with provincial and local government responsible for Integrated Development Plans. The biggest challenge in the VBR is still poverty alleviation and unemployment with approximately 97% of the 1.5 million population still residing in rural areas offering very few economic opportunities.

Agriculture and land

The primary economic generators in the VBR are agriculture and mining, with agriculture by far the biggest employer. The declining trend in the agricultural sector, demonstrated by a reduction from 29% of the district Gross Value Add in 1995 to 24% of the district GVA in 2013, has led to a national policy that 'encourages the growth of agriculture by transforming the apartheid space economy'. The VBR intends to have consultation with Agriculture to discuss the contribution of the biosphere reserve in the transformation of the agricultural practices and to be aligned to the sustainable development principles.

Mining

Mining in the VBR presents opportunities for economic growth and employment, but also results in long-term negative implications on biodiversity. There is a need for the VBR to play a more leading role in trying to promote the conservation of nature while also promoting sustainable development in the biosphere.

Tourism

Conventional Tourism is still a relatively small economic generator although 'research-tourism' and a few other niches that showcase authentic lifestyle-experiences and exclusive nature experiences have increased during the past 10 years. However, the VBR has tourism opportunities presented by the N1 road

that joins the Vhembe District with Zimbabwe , Malawi and Zambia and further north. There is also Nandoni Dam which is a tourist attraction site due to activities such as boating, picnic and the informal fresh fish market. Furthermore, the VBR is also a home of the big five, which are found in the Kruger National Park and the Mapungubwe National Park, which attract a lot of tourists. Local tourism where in Thulamela and Makhado shows transformation in relation to ownership of the hospitality facilities like lodges , hotels and conference facilities owned by previously disadvantaged people

Biosphere Demonstration Projects

The VBR has produced a set of criteria and guidelines that will form the basis of a proposed 'VBR Manual for establishing and promoting Biosphere Demonstration Projects'.

The biggest challenge facing the VBR in the longer term, is to contribute towards the establishment of Biosphere Demonstration Projects which will assist in alleviating poverty and promoting sustainable development and livelihoods in the VBR.

Some of the demonstration projects that have been funded by the VBR include:

- 1) Nombela Gardens
- 2) Vhembe Adopt a River,
- 3) Mashau Light of Mercy,
- 4) World Cup World Parks
- 5) Jalapeo Foundation
- 6) Baobab Foundation

Figure 15: Authentic lifestyle tours to rural villages with traditionally painted homesteads, visiting rural artisans like well-known Thomas Kubayi (photo right) and Lucky Makamu (photo of his work in the middle) and African homestays are on the increase in the VBR

UPDATE ON LOGISTICS

A milestone for Research and Monitoring in the VBR, was the award in 2013, of a 15-year Chair for Biodiversity Value and Change to the University of Venda (UNIVEN) by the South African Research Chairs Initiative (SARChI).

The South African Research Chairs Initiative

Over the last six years, this SARChI Chair produced more than 60 peer-reviewed publications (Appendix J), several popular articles, 50 Honours, MSC and PhD students and five postdoctoral fellowships.

Most of these were intricately linked with biodiversity ecology, ecosystem, services and conservation biology in the VBR.

In recent years, this Chair developed an increasingly, inter-disciplinary and multi-disciplinary focus, with current and completed postdoctoral and PhD studies focussing on topics such as:

- social and environmental impacts of invasive alien species;
- incorporation of heritage and sacred sites and traditional knowledge into biodiversity conservation;
- ecosystem services;
- sustainable natural-pest- control and pollination, and
- Community awareness of natural control and sustainable practices in pest management.

One such long-term study involves a close partnership between UNIVEN, German researchers and the South African macadamia industry to promote sustainable agricultural practices by enhancing natural pest control and pollination services.

The project has been widely and positively disseminated in the commercial agricultural media by one of the country's leading processors of macadamia nuts, Green Farms, situated in the VBR.

South Africa is currently the world's largest macadamia producer and the Levubu valley to the south-east of the Soutpansberg the major macadamia-producing area in the country.

Figure 16: Integrated pest control on Macadamia farms in the Levubu Valley. A Slit faced bat caught a stinkbug causing extensive damage to commercial Macadamia nut production in the Levubu Valley. Photo: Merlin Tuttle.

The VBR has the opportunity to work with various stakeholders (government and private) to demonstrate sustainable development.

The research, capacity building and awareness efforts of the Research Chair on Biodiversity Value and Change in the VBR were amplified considerably by international collaboration and funding approximating R6.5 m since it started. This has contributed significantly to the work of the VBR.

UPDATE ON GOVERNANCE, MANAGEMENT AND COORDINATION

After nomination in 2009, the VBR was run by an NGO which included a chairperson and five task teams. In 2013, the VBR Non-Profit Company was established according to the Companies Act of 2008.

The Board is elected at the AGM and directors may serve for a three-year term. The Board comprises a Chairperson, Vice Chair, a Secretary, Treasurer and board members, which appoints the coordinator and chairs with members of five task teams; all members constitute volunteers for the past ten years. The VBR paid a part-time coordinator between March 2017 and April 2018 and could then afford to appoint a part-time coordinator from the 1st of July 2019 again.

2.3 Authorities in charge

The authorities in charge of coordination and managing the VBR are shown in the diagram below (Figure 17).

The VBR NPC reports to LEDET who then report to the Department of Environment, Forestry and Fisheries (DEFF) who liaise with AfriMAB and UNESCO.

Figure 17 : Reporting structure of the VBR.

Figure 18: One of a thousand splendid Baobab sunsets north or south of the Soutpansberg in the VBR

Figure 19: The sacred lake Fundudzi and more east, hippos in the Levubu River in the Kruger National Park.

UPDATE IN MANAGEMENT POLICY

There has been no change to our management policy, vision and mission in the past 10 years.

According to the VBR Constitution;

The vision of VBR is:

To maximise the VBR's considerable potential for conservation, sustainable development and socio-economic upliftment, as well as research and education in the interests of ensuring long term sustainable benefits for its stakeholders.

This is supported by our mission, which is:

To build a conservation and sustainable-use ethic, which can then be effectively monitored; to promote appropriate and sustainable development; to actively spread benefits and opportunities to disadvantaged members of the community including land resettlement communities; and to facilitate relevant research, education and skills training in the area for the benefit of its stakeholders.

The VBR's objectives are to:

- 1) Participate in the UNESCO MAB programme through relevant government agencies and structures;
- 2) Generate interest and active participation in environmental conservation amongst its members;
- 3) Conserve and enhance the natural environment including ecosystem services, indigenous fauna and flora, mountains and river systems, and its rich cultural heritage and historically important sites;
- 4) Promote the research and preservation of local indigenous knowledge systems (IKS) with appropriate technology for the benefit of the VBR's stakeholders;
- 5) Implement management strategies for the sustainable utilisation of the natural and cultural resources of the area;
- 6) Improve the quality of life of the people in the VBR through the creation of job opportunities through socio-economic upliftment, education, training, skills transfer and capacity building programmes;
- 7) Enhance the sustainable tourism potential and tourism information networks in the VBR;
- 8) Maintain a Biosphere Reserve Centre/Office to provide a local scientific and technical support service relating to all biosphere issues for all the stakeholders in the VBR;
- 9) Participate in joint ventures including but not limited to, Community/Public/Private Partnerships in order to promote the VBR on a local, regional and national scale;
- 10) Subject itself to national and provincial legislation and policies relating to environmental, and IKS issues;
- 11) Conduct appropriate work in collaboration with existing institutions locally, provincially, nationally and internationally; and,

- 12) Co-ordinate all biosphere activities within the VBR according to the principles above and ensure that the activities of the VBR are transparent and conveyed to all stakeholders.

Figure 20: More than 97% of the population live in rural areas of the VBR, relying on subsistence farming and indigenous knowledge systems for survival

BUDGET AND STAFF SUPPORT

The VBR budget (2009-2019) comprised of funding solely from the provincial government, which is LEDET, which was not always sufficient to support VBR operational costs. LEDET provided funds for the operations of the VBR with an annual tranche of ~ R150 000 per annum. These funds were distributed from LEDET via the VDM with whom they have a Memorandum of Agreement to coordinate and manage the VBR and consequently much of the technical studies and subsequent reports were undertaken by volunteers on a no-payment basis or in partnership with UNIVEN..

The VBR NPC faced further challenges since 2009 with receipt of its budget, being often late or not received. This was as a result of the method of payment as outlined above, whereby funds are channelled from LEDET to the VDM and finally to the VBR. The only funding available to the VBR was from this source and without the funding it became exceedingly difficult to operate.

This method meant that a non-payment in 2018 led to the cessation of most operations other than auditing and company registration.

In June 2019, LEDET implemented a mechanism whereby funds are transferred directly to the VBR which should improve the situation substantially.

The VBR has relied on the voluntary work and contributions of directors, members of the task teams and many other individuals and organisations. The contributions of the Lajuma Research Centre, H12 Leshiba, Ndimma Community Services, UNIVEN, the Mountain Inn Hotel and the EWT are acknowledged. These organisations provided logistical support as hosting venues, seminars and for assisting researchers with much needed assistance in the field.

From 2011 to 2014 the VDM was in control of financial support for the VBR and issued payments against the budgets as set by the Board. The figures from 2014 onwards in the table below, are those that the VBR NPC received from LEDET directly (Table 5).

In addition, the VBR received a transfer of R94 050 from the VDM in May 2017 to support demonstration projects outside of the VBR operational budget. In 2019 the VBR received an amount of

R79 131, 18 from the German Commission for UNESCO to help with stakeholder engagements for the Ten Year Periodic Review.

Table 5 : The VBR budget with amounts received (2009-2020)

Year	VBR Budget	Funds received	Details
2009-2011	N/A	N/A	No funds were allocated
2011-2012	100 000	100 000	Funds administered from VDM to make payments for VBR
2012-2013	100 000	100 000	
2013-2014	140 000	140 000	Funds administered from VDM to make payments for VBR; R73 890 transferred to VBR for specific budget items
2014-2015	151 000	151 000	R141 500 received June & July 2015
2015-2016	200 000	200 000	R200 000 received 14.09.2017 (LEDET)
2016-2017	217 000	217 000	R217 000 received 15.07.2019 (LEDET)
2017-2018	233 000	Pending	N/A
2018-2019	N/A	233 000	R233 000 received 15.03.2019 (LEDET)
2019	n/a	R79 131, 18	Funds from German Commission for UNESCO
2019-2020	250 000	250 000	Received February 2020 (LEDET)

LEDET received support from GEF and were able to fund six projects in the VBR.

This amounted to US \$ 204 000/ R2 679 000 and were distributed as indicated in table 6 below.

Table 6 : Recipients in the VBR of the GEF funds with amounts

Recipient	Amount (ZAR)		Amount (US\$)
Mubvumoni Project for the Disabled	529 940		40 000
Nombhela Botanical Garden and Cultural village	529 940		40 000
Matavhela Greenery	529 940		40 000
Dzomo la Mupo	364 000		28 000
Pfariso Yashu	364 000		28 000
Tshikofokofo and Adopt a River	364 000		28 000

The VBR provided financial assistance to three Biosphere Demonstration Projects during the years 2017 to 2018: 1) Nombhela Nursery, 2) Adopt a River Project, and 3) Baobab Foundation.

Each of these Demonstration Projects was allocated R30 000, for the purchase of equipment and covering costs for public events.

Figure 21: In the rural communities, children play soccer on dusty fields, artisans recycle old tires to make sandals and people build mud houses with thatched roofs from local materials in the VBR.

COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

One of the VBR's greatest challenges has been its inability to communicate the work of the VBR to its more than 1.5 million stakeholders. This has largely been due to lack of funds and the enormity of the task but is also due to the lack of committed members to emulate the work of the Conservation Task Team who have achieved remarkable success relying on volunteers.

LEDET has been through the years conducting awareness to residents within Vhembe about the biosphere, which has significantly contributed to the support from local communities. The Women and

Environment Programme encourages women to participate in solving environmental challenges, during the months of August women organize celebrations and VBR is part of the celebrations.

Also the Green Community Projects, held within the VBR wherein communities are encouraged to apply for funding. We have projects such as Adopt a river, Wetlands conservation, Subsistence agriculture, Land care, tourism projects and arts and culture which are administered in the VBR

Communication with various stakeholders has improved with the appointment of the new Board Coordinator in July 2019. Despite this challenge, there has been some success in the last 10 years in promoting the VBR, some of which are outlined below:

- 1) Road sign boards at all the major entry roads to the VBR have been erected to raise awareness for visitors to the area (Figure 22).

Figure 22: Image showing the VBR road sign on the N1 highway

2) The VBR have created a website since its nomination in 2009 and is active on Facebook (with almost 1000 followers; Figure 23), Instagram and Twitter:

- Website VBR: www.vhembebiosphere.org
- Facebook: [Vhembebiosphere](https://www.facebook.com/vhembebiosphere),
- Twitter: [@Vhembebiosphere](https://twitter.com/Vhembebiosphere)
- Instagram: [@Vhembebiosphere](https://www.instagram.com/Vhembebiosphere)

Figure 23: Two images from the VBR Facebook site.

3) The SARChI chair has a [separate website](#) linked to the VBR through UNIVEN, which boosted communication substantially in the VBR³.

As a vibrant hub for biodiversity science, training and conservation application in the Southern African Development Community with a body of established and emerging researchers, postgraduate and postdoctoral candidates, it generates support for the VBR in kind and resulted in substantial financial contributions as well.

4) In December 2017, the VBR hosted a Communications Strategy Workshop in collaboration with UNESCO at the Indigenous Knowledge Centre at Leshiba in the western Soutpansberg (Figure 24).

The workshop was facilitated by a programme specialist from the UNESCO MAB Programme, as well as a director from WITHIN People⁴.

³ <http://www.univen.ac.za/sarchi/>

⁴ <https://www.withinpeople.com/>

This formed part of the UNESCO Global Strategy that was developed by WITHIN People for the UNESCO MAB programme. The workshop sessions included exploring and understanding the global UNESCO Communications strategy that would develop a VBR Story that aligns to the global strategy. Written in a layperson idiom the VBR Story titled '*Celebrate life in the land of Legend*', is now used to engage with stakeholders, is incorporated to the website, became the key message for promotion and raising awareness for the VBR and became the first step towards the development of a VBR Communication Strategy.

Figure 24: Delegates attending a Communications Strategy Workshop in collaboration with UNESCO at the *Indigenous Knowledge Centre at Leshiba in the western Soutpansberg*

STRATEGIES FOSTERING NETWORKS

The SARChI Research Chair on 'Biodiversity Value and Change in the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve' has been the VBR's main and champion networker. It developed an increasingly inter- and multi-disciplinary focus in recent years, with current and completed postdoctoral and PhD studies focussing on topics such as; incorporation of heritage and sacred sites and traditional knowledge into biodiversity conservation, ecosystem services and ecological restoration initiatives.

Other topics focussed on; sustainable natural pest control and pollination in macadamia and mango orchards of commercial farmers in the Levubu Valley and community awareness of natural control and sustainable practices in rodent pest management on rural small-holder communities.

The Chair also contributed, as a principal investigator, on two successive and ongoing international projects funded by the European Union and African Union. These projects examined [ecologically-based rodent management](#) in rural small-holders at villages in the east of VBR. Outputs of one of these projects

included extensive agricultural extension material for small-scale farmers in Africa and Madagascar including discussion papers and videos on how to control rodents.

Postdoctoral research will lead to the development of community-based management plans for supporting ecological restoration initiatives on Vhavenda community rangelands. The management plans will guide the work of the community-based organisation Dzomo La Mupo through the planting of indigenous tree species in degraded riverine and forest environments of villages situated outside the Thathe-Vondo and Entabeni Forestry Reserves (Figure 25).

Figure 25: Thathe-Vondo Sacred Site

From 2019-2020, documented Vhavenda indigenous knowledge of culturally significant tree species and sustainable practices will be developed into a book, detailing important ethnobotanical uses and traditional management systems for forest management for Vhavenda communities and schools in the Vhembe District.

Figure 26: The VBR's Research and Education task team network and collaborate with the Dzomo la Mupo Foundation through the planting of indigenous tree species in degraded riverine and forest environments of villages situated outside the Thathe-Vondo and Entabeni Forestry Reserves in the Eastern Soutpansberg. Photos: Mphatheleni Makaulule

The VBR has been working with various companies through their Corporate Social Investment and supports the Nombhela Community Project and Adopt a River Project. These two projects cover over 50 villages where local communities are involved in cleaning of local rivers.

The Board and task teams have met over the past 10 years to discuss a range of issues and challenges facing the VBR. Topics and interaction including the following:

- 1) The threat and environmental challenges of large-scale mining;
- 2) The interaction with commercial farmers and local communities;
- 3) Formulating and promoting the Stewardship Programme;
- 4) Engagement with government sector departments, through attendance at Vhembe Land Development Forum meetings and workshops;
- 5) Interaction and the involvement with local municipalities;
- 6) The participation and contribution towards the Limpopo Conservation Plan and the Vhembe Bioregional Plan; and,
- 7) Cooperation with SANParks and the GMTFCA.

VISION AND APPROACHES FOR SOCIO-CULTURAL CONTEXT.

Promotion of local heritage resources

Given the rich, local culture and heritage within the VBR, there has been a need to document and preserve these practices and physical sites. The VBR has encouraged the undertaking of a regional plan to identify all the heritage and sacred places and practices with this process having started during the review period.

Vhembe Biosphere Heritage Database Project

Ndimba Community Services (NCS) is currently compiling a heritage-sites database of sites found in the VBR. The main objective is to identify the heritage hotspots. The project also includes face-to-face interviews with stakeholders to gather information on how the local communities manage their heritage sites and the challenges that they face. In addition, NCS also questioned stakeholders on their knowledge of the existence of the VBR, biospheres and their roles in general. Findings of this project will be available soon. NCS seeks to undertake a feasibility study for establishing an indigenous knowledge centre (I-Centre) in the VBR. The aim of an I-Centre is to assist all VBR stakeholders, such as school children, tourists, diviners and researchers, to display and preserve the rich cultural knowledge in the VBR. NLC are currently working on their application to NLC for funding to construct the I-Centre.

USE OF TRADITIONAL AND LOCAL KNOWLEDGE

Local indigenous knowledge systems (IKS) is an important asset of the VBR and has developed over many centuries. It is still practiced amongst many residents of the VBR, especially in rural villages. IKS is acknowledged and recognised by the South African government as well as local institutions such as UNIVEN, as a powerful basis through which the rich cultural heritage of the VBR can be preserved. It can also be a cost-effective way to improve the lives of people in innovative ways.

Figure 27: Left: Construction using traditional materials merged with appropriate technology at Leshiba H12 cultural village. Right : One of the huts at the IKS centre at H12 Leshiba.

Figure 28: Well-known local artist, Noria Mabasa's, adobe sculptures at H12 Leshiba's Venda village lodge

In the VBR, IKS covers aspects such as the use of traditional medicinal and aromatic plants, traditional music instruments, crafts and art, the growing and use of local indigenous food-plants and building methods suitable for our climate and environment. There is general recognition that this knowledge, combined with appropriate technology could assist in poverty alleviation, improvement to nutrition, and the encouragement of eco-and cultural tourism. Traditional building techniques, craft-skills and

knowledge merged with appropriate new technology is for example used to establish a unique eco lodge from the original Venda Village idea at Leshiba H12 in the Western Soutpansberg (Figure 27 & 28).

The VBR collaborate with organisations such as Ndima Community Services and [Dzomo la Mupo \(DLM\)](#) in the Vhembe District and surrounding areas where they play a critical role in promoting the use of traditional knowledge systems, particularly around sacred sites such as Lake Fundudzi.

Lake Fundudzi and the adjacent and associated sacred forests of Thate-Vondo has been protected by deploying indigenous knowledge systems for centuries, and although some sites have been disturbed, much of the area is still pristine. DLM works to revive local and indigenous knowledge systems related to the revival of women's traditional leadership positions for land and agriculture, environmental education and cultural biodiversity preservation.

They also engage primary and secondary schools through workshops and inter-generational learning exchanges with elders and youth to unearth indigenous knowledge of the environment, and to strengthen respect for the traditional roles of elders as knowledge holders in rural communities.

DLM has recently received funding from the GEF to support schools in their region with an education programme and the revival of plant-based knowledge through inter-generational learning exchanges, tree planting initiatives in the Venda region and to support the women's indigenous plant nurseries.

The VBR also supports and promotes the work of [Madi a Thavha Mountain Lodge](#) in their support of local artisans developing heritage-based craft products for high end markets. This work includes the preservation of dwindling local IKS by intentionally bringing together young artisans with experienced crafters in workshops at their rural villages or at their cultural heritage centre at the lodge. Madi a Thavha also promotes local art and culture at their Dancing Fish Gallery and Textile & Design studio; they source, promote and market local Limpopo arts and crafts in their CraftArt Centre in Johannesburg too, especially those that engage with the rich cultural heritage of Limpopo.

COMMUNITY CULTURAL DEVELOPMENT INITIATIVES.

Leshiba Centre for Indigenous Knowledge and Appropriate Technology

The Leshiba Centre for Indigenous Knowledge and Appropriate Technology (IKC) is part of the Leshiba Wildlife and Ecotourism Lodge situated on top of the western Soutpansberg; Leshiba is [accredited by Fair Trade](#) and is an active member of the VBR.

The IKC focuses on promoting sustainable development by understanding and utilising IKS combined with appropriate technology through five sub-themes for research and development: 1) Arts, crafts and materials, 2) Traditional medicine and health, 3) Indigenous food systems, 4) Building technology, 5) Indigenous Knowledge at the interface with other systems of knowledge). Leshiba has offered various workshops in the framework of these sub-themes since 2000. One of the flagship operations at Leshiba is the permaculture garden used in their restaurant and for skills development.

Madi a Thavha Mountain Lodge

The NGO, [Tourism Conservation Fund](#) (TCF) partnered with two VBR members and enterprises: Madi a Thavha Mountain Lodge and Traditional African Homestays South Africa (TAHS-SA). The TCF seeks to protect and promote the biodiversity of South Africa's conservation areas by investing in adjacent communities to create sustainable businesses and jobs which are rooted in the wildlife-tourism economy. Through commercial partnerships of different kinds, they aim to build a more inclusive wildlife-tourism economy in which a growing share of the value accrues to historically excluded households and communities.

Figure 29: Makuleke community residents during a TCF-Madi a Thavha Craft-workshop at Makuleke

[Madi a Thavha Mountain Lodge](#) collaborates with TCF through a matched-funding partnership; this is between Madi a Thavha and the Makuleke community, which borders Kruger National Park, at Punda Maria (Figure 29). Together they support 15 newly identified artisans to establish and run a commercial CraftArt business. Based on cultural heritage and Indigenous Knowledge and skills, these artisans are equipped to produce and sell quality products in high value craft markets from which they were historically excluded (Figure 30).

Figure 30: Heritage-based products developed by Madi a Thavha Mountain Lodge with rural artisans in the VBR for high end markets.

Madi a Thavha is a Fair-Trade in Tourism lodge in the Soutpansberg, a member of the VBR and one of our finest models of sustainable development. The lodge house a Cultural Heritage Centre in which the history and cultural heritage of Limpopo since stone-age times are on colourful display. They work with the local Venda, Tsonga and Lobedo people documenting, presenting, promoting and assisting local artisans to build upon their rich cultural heritage through arranging village tours and selling their art and craft to, mostly international tourists in the region. Madi a Thavha employ local people, source heritage-based produce locally and provide product development and business training to more than 30 artisans and craft producers in Vhembe, 20 of whom in 2019 were amongst the 80 artisans shortlisted for the Innibos South African National Craft Awards. They have recently opened a CraftArt centre at Victoria Yards, an inner-city regeneration project in Johannesburg, to enable artisans from Limpopo to display and sell their work and where cross pollination between rural and urban skills and knowledge are encouraged with artisans-in-residence programs and workshops. Madi a Thavha and Victoria Yards have the same business approach which is as much about social development as it is about commercial enterprise. Madi a Thavha won a silver award in the World Responsible Tourism Awards of 2018 in the category: Best for Local Economic Benefit.

Traditional African Homestays South Africa

Traditional African Homestays South Africa (TAHS-SA) TCF finalised a Business Linkage Fund partnership contract with tour operator [Abang Africa Travel](#) and [TAHS-SA](#), a local organisation that engages with communities and provides the necessary tools and training so that the community is able to open their homes to local and international tourists to offer them real authentic tourism experiences (Figure 31). Sustainable tourism practices are utilised as a vehicle to uplift and support local communities. It is a participatory process through which rural communities learn over time, through their own experiences and initiatives, how to adapt their indigenous knowledge to a changing world and to allow this knowledge to form part of tourism products within the context of their own time, space and conditions.

The homestay initiative directly contributes to the income of homestay mothers, the guides, the activity hosts (such as, traditional cooking lessons, beading, dancing), local markets, artists and importantly the moral of the community.

Figure 31: Since the Traditional African Homestays project was launched in August 2017, Makushu-Mosholombi village has hosted more than 50 international guests and 45 local guests until July 2018

Since the project was launched on 29 August 2017, Makushu-Mosholombi Village has hosted more than 50 international guests and 45 local guests. The program has enabled 25 homestay mothers to open their homes for international guests, 10 guides to be trained as local guides, and a whole community to be included in the tourism value chain.

The bookings also contributed to a local non-profit organisation, Tshikhala, and the village fund, Gondoliswa, that runs the old age home and crèche.

TAH SA received special recognition at the national [Lilizela Tourism Awards](#) in 2018 for their creative way of embracing tourism as a vessel for change in their community, when they became the first winner of the new, *I Do Tourism Award in 2018*.

LANGUAGES IN THE VBR

Twelve languages are utilised in the VBR, of which one is sign language (Table 7).

Table 7 : Languages identified in the VBR

Language	% of population in the VBR which speaks each language
Tshivenda	69.3%
Tsonga	24.9%
Northern Sotho	1.6%
Sotho	1.0%
Afrikaans	1.3%

English	1.0%
Ndebele	0.3%
Tswana	0.1%
Swati	0.2%
Sign	0.1%
Xhosa	0.1%
Zulu	1.0%
Other	2.1%

The majority of Vhembe residents speak Tshivenda (approximately 800 000) with approximately 300 000 residents speaking Xitsonga. The rest of the languages spoken in the VBR are listed according to the percentage of the population in the table above. There are no endangered languages in the VBR.

MANAGEMENT EFFECTIVENESS

The management effectiveness of the biosphere reserve is assessed through the VBR NPC Board, reporting to LEDET and DEFF as well as stakeholders attending the AGM. This involves a review of the implementation reports of various projects identified and approved by the Board. In addition, the Core Areas such as Mapungubwe National Park, Kruger National Park and provincial nature reserves, currently use the Management Effectiveness Tool (version 3). This is a tool developed to assess all protected areas that are managed by the South African government and its agencies. It is a self-assessment tool by protected area authorities, which is also followed by verification missions. The METT score is determined through a questionnaire which protected area authorities' management should respond to. The work and effectiveness of the VBR NPC has been limited by the lack of financial resources, however, volunteer work has led to much progress broadening the stakeholder base, responding to developmental issues and registering the VBR as an NPC.

Conservation Task Team

Over the last ten years they have worked on the conservation issues in the VBR, collaborating with national, provincial government they have also contributed towards the Limpopo Conservation Plan. They are also currently working on expanding the conserved areas in the VBR through stewardship program around the Soutpansberg mountain range area.

Research Task Team

This had been the most active and successful of the task teams. Headed by Prof Peter Taylor from the University of Venda they have managed to conduct a lot of research linked to the biosphere model. They have also managed to attract international researchers to the VBR to study the rich biodiversity we have

in the area and also look at sustainable livelihoods linked development programs. The University of Venda has played an important role in the research within the VBR.

Development Task Team

The development task team has also been active in the region mostly by raising awareness and contribution to discussion on environmental impact assessments in the biosphere. They have actively participated in the discussion of the Special Economic Zones establishment in the biosphere.

Communication and Awareness

This task team managed to conduct a communication workshop with UNESCO MaB to try and design the communications strategy for the VBR. Current work involves revamping the VBR website and other social media platforms as well as developing an Application which can be used by stakeholders.

The VBR has made tremendous strides in interacting with different stakeholders and communities and this is an ongoing process. We have been involved in various meetings with Traditional leaderships, Community Based Organisations, district and local municipality community outreach programs. Over the last ten years at most events organised by LEDET there has been a slot reserved for biospheres, showing their support towards the program.

We have the Greenest Municipality competition: all the four local municipality (Thulamela, Musina, Makhado and Collins Chabane) participate; the main purpose is to look after their environment; the focus of the competition is as follow: 1) Waste management 2) Energy efficiency and conservation 3) Water management 4) Landscaping, tree planting and beautification 5) Leadership and institutional arrangement 6) Public participation and community empowerment and schools

Fortunately, the Core Areas such as Mapungubwe National Park, Kruger National Park and provincial nature reserves, are managed by government institutions which currently use the Management Effectives Tool (version 3)..

2.4 Matters of special interest

LOCAL, REGIONAL AND NATIONAL PLANS

The VBR is included in the Vhembe District Municipality Integrated Development Plan (IDP) as one of the programmes which assist in large landscape management and the promotion of their sustainable development agenda. The municipality IDPs are updated every three years to ensure that they address the needs for the identified period.

The VBR has also been part of ,and supported the Vhembe District Bioregional Plan of 2017 in which the Critical Biodiversity Areas (CBAs) and Ecological Support Areas (ESAs), forming part of the Limpopo Conservation Plan V2, 2013 (LCPv2) were discussed in terms of *inter alia*, physical aspects and various planning instruments and informants (such as, guidelines for decision-making). These guidelines provide a framework for land-uses compatible with the land management objectives of each category on the Map of CBAs.

The guidelines were used in conjunction with other sector-specific guidelines applicable within the Province, such as *Mining and Biodiversity Guideline* (SANBI, 2013), *Atlas of Freshwater Ecosystem Priority Areas for South Africa* (Nel et al., 2011), *Limpopo Protected Area Expansion Strategy Technical Report* (Desmet et al., 2014), *Implementation Manual for Freshwater Ecosystem Priority Areas* (Driver et al., 2011) and our *Vhembe Biosphere Reserve's Initial SEMP: Desired State of the Environment Report with Environmental Management Guidelines* (SEF, 2016).

SANParks has integrated the VBR into their buffer zone management plan whilst DEFF has compiled a strategy for the management of biosphere reserves of which the VBR is a part.

The Provincial Conservation plan (LCPv2) has provided a basis for the future Environmental Management Framework (EMF) for the VBR, of which the VBR was included in the development of the plan.

OUTCOMES OF COOPERATION PLANS

The Conservation Task Team has benefited tremendously with the input and cooperation from the work emanating from Professor Peter Taylor's unit at UNIVEN. In addition, the work undertaken by the EWT and its Stewardship Programme, as well as the Work for Water group all contributed towards long-term sustainable development in the VBR.

There is a need to improve the integration of the local authorities' IDP plans and those of the VDM with the above. Furthermore, there is a critical need for the Department of Mineral Resources to cooperate with the VBR in assessing future mining applications in the area.

Figure 32: Left: Makgabeng. Right: The gold-plated Rhino (dated 900 - 1300 AD) from Mapungubwe National Park

INVOLVEMENT OF LOCAL COMMUNITIES

Research partnerships between Dr Constant and Tonderai Makoni at UNIVEN and Dzomo La Mupo have engaged rural Vhavenda communities around the rural villages of Thathe-Vondo and Entabeni forestry complexes in the eastern parts of the VBR, on issues related to the protection of sacred natural sites, reviving indigenous agriculture and forest management practices, and restoration of riverine and forest landscapes on indigenous lands.

These research partnerships have contributed to informing sustainable practices for land management through education workshops with rural communities, tree planting activities, and plans to develop education materials for communities and schools in these regions.

Every year the following public awareness are conducted in collaboration with local, provincial and national government namely: world wetland day, world environment day and habitat day, when they are celebrated presentations are done and Biosphere is one of the item.

Limpopo green school for the Earth is another program which is run in the VBR by LEDET and it involve the selection of 21 school in all four local Municipality, they participate under the following themes: energy, water conservation, landscaping, tree planting, and waste management.

Conserving and promotion of cultural heritage and IKS by private enterprises and members of the VBR, (as mentioned above) will ensure that traditional knowledge and skills in local communities is kept alive by finding new applications for indigenous knowledge and by merging appropriate technologies with indigenous skills to develop and promote traditional skills and relevant aspects of cultural heritage.

Through funding from the German commission for UNESCO, VBR has managed to carry out stakeholder engagements with various stakeholders in the biosphere. Meetings have been held with traditional leaders, youths, local government and the general populace in each of the 5 local municipalities which cover the VBR. This is a continuous process wherein we go out and engage the people even in schools to talk to people and try to show them how they can play a role in the biosphere.

WOMEN'S ROLES

Women are given equal opportunity to participate in the VBR and in many cases given preference. In rural community projects, women representation is, on average, above 60%. The province emphasises and encourages the formation of Women and Environment committees to deal with environmental issues. The organisation, Adopt-a-River, for example, is mainly run by rural women. Adopt a River, collect waste and clean river systems. This forum is established in all five local municipalities of the VBR. During the past

5 years, GEF (Global Environmental Facility) funded six projects, mainly led by women and administered directly through LEDET (not by the VBR NPC) in the VBR's rural landscape (Table 8).

Table 8: GEF funded projects, primarily supporting women in the VBR (demonstration projects)

Recipient	Details
Mubvumoni Project for the Disabled	A project for disabled people situated in Mubvumoni in the Thulamela Local Municipality, funded in 2017.
Nombhela Botanical Garden and Cultural Village	A community driven NPO at Njakanjaka Village. Activities include agro-ecology, propagation of vines, tourism development and creation of parks, funded in 2017.
Matavhela Greenery	Matavhela Greenery Primary Cooperatives Ltd started in 2015 with the vision to cover the national curriculum in primary schools. The project is involved in the greenery initiatives for unemployed female groups mainly at rural schools.
Dzomo la Mupo	A non-profit organisation established in 2007 for indigenous tree planting, recuperation of indigenous food and medicinal plants and indigenous knowledge.
Pfariso Yashu	Pfariso Yashu Community Centre is an NPO established in 2009. They help child-headed family-orphans and vulnerable children in Mashau-Bodwe villages under the Makhado Local Municipality in the VBR. The Centre focuses on four areas: 1) Support of learners' work, 2) Providing food after school, 3) Facilitating a permaculture, and 4) Scout programme. The grant was given for the period 2019 – 2020.
Tshikofokofo and Adopt a River	Tshikofokofo and Adopt a River was started in 2010 as an NPO. The project aims to empower people through life skills and leadership training programmes. Project activities include removing and collecting of solid waste in the water bodies in their immediate environment, clearing

littering in the villages and making waste collection facilities. Funded 2018 to 2020.

VBR-member Madi a Thavha’s Textile & Design studio trains local women at ‘drop-in centres’ (i.e. after-school centres for vulnerable children, such as the Vhutshilo Mountain School for HIV/AIDS orphans and vulnerable young adults and the Refugee Centre in Makhado’ Figure 33), to sew and design their own clothes and to make interior products, such as curtains and cushions. These can either be for themselves or to sell as an income. Most of the textiles used are traditional Venda or Tsonga prints.

Figure 33 : Madi a Thavha Mountain Lodge supported Vutshilo Mountain School for HIV/AIDS orphans and vulnerable women and children, through various funding projects and skills training

CHANGES IN MAIN PROTECTION REGIME OF CORE AREAS AND BUFFER ZONES

There are no changes in the main protection regime of the existing Core Areas and Buffer Zones of the VBR. There are proposed plans to review the buffer zone for the Mapungubwe National Park and World Heritage Site. The VBR participates in this process (Appendix G).

RESEARCH AND MONITORING ACTIVITIES IN THE VBR

The VBR has a MoU with the UNIVEN in terms of research and monitoring in the VBR. UNIVEN has conducted numerous research projects in the past 10 years on the following thematic areas:

- Biodiversity conservation
- Ecosystem services and livelihoods
- Invasion biology
- Global change

Several other notable organisations also undertake research and monitoring activities in the VBR, of which a few are highlighted below:

- The South African National Botanical Institute (SANBI) <https://www.sanbi.org/biodiversity/building-knowledge/biodiversity-monitoring-assessment/national-biodiversity-assessment/> is responsible for conducting National Biodiversity Assessments, which also includes the VBR. The Mara Agricultural Research Council under the provincial Department of Agriculture and Rural Development is responsible for agricultural research in animal husbandry and game farming in the VBR.
- Several NGO's are conducting research on biodiversity assessment and conservation in the VBR, which also involve expertise from overseas countries. These include the Endangered Wildlife Trust, Lajuma Research Centre <http://www.lajuma.com/> and Mogalakwena Research Centre <http://www.researchlimpopo.com/>.
- Schoemansdal Environmental Centre has conducted environmental education with large school groups under the Department of Education for the past 10 years.
- The Madzivhandila Agricultural College trains surrounding communities on agricultural-related programmes for food security; they are also responsible for food gardens in the region, crop production and agricultural schemes.
- The Vhembe Technical and Vocational Education and Training colleges (T.V.E.T) assist in the training of quality-assured and responsive skills-based programmes for life-long learning. There is one TVET college in each of the local Municipalities with specific training in agriculture, mechanical and IT technologies.

Figure 34: The confluence of the Shashe and Limpopo Rivers, where three countries meet; Botswana, Zimbabwe and South Africa in the Mapungubwe National Park - a World Heritage Site. Photo: Wendy Collinson

STRENGTHENING OF COLLECTIVE CAPACITIES OF GOVERNANCE

The provincial government has established the Provincial Biosphere Forum which includes all key institutions within the Province. Stakeholders meet every quarter. LEDET has an MOU with all three biospheres which helps to regulate the interactions between the department and them, and promoted good governance by regulating reporting, finances, communication. The Province has three designated biosphere reserves, and the Forum assists in sharing the best practices amongst them.

The VBR is also part of the National MAB Committee represented by its Board Chairperson and Coordinator. Involvement in provincial and national forums has allowed the sharing of experience and strategies.

The history of the development of South African biosphere reserves established earlier than the VBR, as communicated through these forums, has also enabled the VBR to learn from their experiences in its own development.

INFORMATION ABOUT THE INTERACTION BETWEEN THE THREE ZONES.

The representatives of the 3 different zones (core, buffer and transitional) forms part of the Board of Directors as well as Technical Committee which serves as advisory body to the Board. These representatives meet on quarterly basis to discuss different aspects of the biosphere reserve. Regular updates on the implementation of various activities is provided to the above-mentioned meetings, which makes it lot easier to coordinate activities within the three zones.

PARTICIPATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE

The VBR Youth Forum was established in June 2019, following the launch of the UNESCO Youth Forum in Italy in September 2017 attended by a representative of the VBR. The VBR Youth Forum focuses mainly on capacity building initiatives.

After the first UNESCO MAB Youth Forum in 2017 in Italy, the VBR board appointed a Youth Coordinator to help establish the VBR Youth Network and mobilise young people to actively participate in VBR activities. UNIVEN assisted with facilities for meetings on campus. With the help of the VBR Coordinator at the time, programs were formulated to reach out to young people.

In 2018, the Youth forum assisted with the Eco-school-programme at Mphaphuli Secondary School, where they helped to teach school children about renewable energy and other environmental related topics.

They have worked closely with an organisation called the Mathematic Solution Skills Development Centre which operates mainly in rural schools in the Collins Chabane Municipality. High-school learners were

taught about careers in science. The goal of the Youth Forum is to help young people design sustainable projects to reap benefits from utilizing their available resources.

Since 2015, Dzomo La Mupo within VBR, have been working closely with schools in the Vhembe District to develop inter-generational learning workshops with elders and youth in schools.

The aim is to create maps of their traditional territories, and rural landscapes to elicit indigenous knowledge of their land and natural resources, and to create collective visions for its protection.

Elders and youth also create seasonal calendars tracking the phenology and planting and harvesting cycles of indigenous plant crops and trees, to learn about the characteristics of different plant species.

These exchanges encourage dialogue and exchanges between elders and youth, to revive indigenous based knowledge, and encourage respect and strengthening of the role of elders in rural communities.

In all the engagements that the VBR does with the community we try to encourage young people to organise themselves in groups and come up with projects that benefit them and the environment. Most of the important environmental calendar dates celebrations are organised and carried out by our VBR Youth Network.

VBR hosted the African Youth Biodiversity Forum in February 2020 and this was a huge achievement for the youth in the VBR. The event brought together about 60 young people from about 28 countries in Africa with the objective of discussing the Post2020 Global Biodiversity Framework. The Forum was meant to discuss how young people can be involved in the discussion for biodiversity both at local and international level.

VBR stakeholders have also seen the need to have young people at the forefront of championing biodiversity and sustainable development matters. At the last elective Annual General Meeting a young lady who is a university student was elected into the Board of Directors.

3 ECOSYSTEM SERVICES

3.1 Update in ecosystem services and its beneficiaries.

The VBR is rich in biodiversity, and the human impacts on ecosystem services are extremely complex. Some scientific studies on ecosystem services and the negative impacts have been undertaken in the VBR (Constant, 2020)

The following are particularly vulnerable in the VBR:

Stabilising and regulatory processes

- Removal of vegetation for cultivation, energy, by overgrazing and through altered burning regimes impacts negatively on the hydrological cycle (flood and drought mitigation).
- The VBR is fed by the Limpopo River system and this system presently only yields 80% of the water required for human development in its catchment area. Water requirements by the extensive mining developments in the biosphere will impact negatively on the availability of water.
- Invertebrates and certain bat species are important pest control agents, but unfortunately commercial farmers are not always aware of this.

Over the past few years, the Chair on Biodiversity Value and Change as well as the Department of Zoology at UNIVEN have undertaken valuable work to make farmers aware of this important ecosystem function.

Regenerating processes

- There is little information of the impact of living organisms on soil generation or fertility in the VBR. However, if the trends recorded in some other parts of the world also apply here, it could have severe negative impacts on natural ecosystems and food production.
- The Ecosystem integrity is being compromise by the existence of alien invasive species and extraction of water for agriculture (particularly for macadamia farms and forest plantation in the east).
- Insect populations have not been monitored to determine whether numbers are declining as in some other parts of the world. There could be serious negative impacts on pollination of key commercial crops, such as macadamia nuts, citrus, tomatoes and potatoes and subtropical crops (such as avocados, bananas, mangoes and guavas) in the VBR.

- A wide range of animal species including invertebrates, birds and many mammal species (particularly primates), fulfil a crucial role in seed dispersal. Reduction in numbers and the size of distribution ranges of these species can have a serious negative impact on the recruitment of plants.

Figure 35: Left: The Phiphidi waterfall in the eastern Soutpansberg is a sacred site for the VhaVenda people. Middle: Indigenous lily in bloom Right: Pockets of pristine bush on top of the Soutpansberg Mountains above Louis Trichardt.

Production of goods

- Various studies have shown that poor rural communities are dependent on wild fruits, animals and insects, for sustenance. The sale of dried mopane worms is also a valuable source of income in some communities in the VBR. One commercial venture in the VBR has created a significant number of jobs through the marketing of Baobab oil and pulp extraction.
- Wood is still an important source of energy and building material in rural parts of the VBR and studies have shown over-utilisation in certain areas, not only by residents but also by people entering the areas from outside.
- Traditional medicine, based on natural products is still widely practiced in the VBR and over-utilisation commonly occurs, partly due to collection by outsiders for markets in Gauteng and elsewhere. The VBR is assisting a project aimed at the production of medicinal species in Thohoyandou.

Figure 36: One of many beautiful views from the Soutpansberg Mountain in the VBR

Life-fulfilling services

- The wilderness character and vast biodiversity of most of the VBR provides ample opportunities for the enjoyment and appreciation of the natural environment through activities such as, hiking, fishing, bird watching, Big 5 tourism, and hunting. This is an extremely valuable resource for the region and has tremendous potential for expansion and job creation. This resource must be protected and managed carefully to ensure that it is not destroyed by irresponsible development or mining.
- The VBR is rich in cultural diversity which adds hugely to the quality of life through cultural, intellectual and spiritual inspiration. A report by the VBR is being compiled to ensure that this resource is conserved for future generations.
- Pristine natural environments in the VBR provide opportunities for life enrichment through scientific discovery for nature lovers and scientists. Several research tourism and serious research centres are situated in the VBR. These centres not only generate the inflow of foreign currency and creation of local job opportunities, but also helps to develop local expertise in biodiversity assessment and management.
- The rich biodiversity and variation in geomorphology of the VBR provides options that will support society as it adapts to climate change.

3.2 Changes in ecosystem service indicators used to evaluate three functions.

The most significant negative impacts on ecosystem services in the VBR over the past decade were:

- 1) Habitat destruction due to population growth and the concomitant growth of residential areas;
- 2) An increase in commercial crop production and exotic forestry;
- 3) Climate change;
- 4) Mining;

Figure 37: Landscapes in the VBR range from pockets of subtropical indigenous forests to arid bushveld

The following are studies that highlight more specific changes to the ecosystem that could be a concern if left unmonitored:

Evans (2017), found that the extent of transformed land in the VBR (based on satellite imagery), reduced by 53% over a 24-year period (from 1990 to 2014), although, this is an over-estimation due to the invasion of former disturbed areas by pioneer plants and exotic vegetation. However, regardless of this, there must have been a reduction in unvegetated areas created by wood collection and commercial or subsistence agriculture and a change in socio-economic conditions (that is, the introduction of social grants and better distribution of electricity) also played a role.

With a population growth rate of around 1.6% per annum, urban expansion occurred and impacted negatively on ecosystem services. Of serious concern are disposable diapers increasingly being illegally dumped in the dongas in the bush and by the side of the roads. ending up along rivers of the VBR.

Hahn (2017), presents evidence of the impact of unsustainable agricultural practices and possibly in part climate change, on ecosystems. One of the ecosystems, namely high rainfall grasslands, became extinct due to a combination of negative impacts, particularly after 1920, and were replaced by bush encroachment. At least 14 large mammal species disappeared from the area either directly or indirectly due to the demise of grasslands.

The potential negative impact of mining on ecosystem services in the VBR is still a serious cause of concern, particularly due to the escalating number of prospecting and mining permits that are issued. The VBR has engaged with mining companies and scrutinised all available impact assessments to try and limit the impact. The impact of mining has been limited to date but if all coal-bearing areas are mined it could destroy up to 26% of the surface area of the VBR (Evans, 2017).

The negative influence of climate change is already felt and is expected to have an escalating impact on ecosystem services in future. This does not only apply to the direct impacts of higher temperatures, droughts or floods, but also to the more gradual impact of climate change on ecosystems and species. Studies by Professor Peter Taylor and his students of UNIVEN have demonstrated that the entire species-rich small-mammal community in parts of the VBR (eg. Sourveld grasslands) are at high risk from climate change as evidenced by papers published on vlei rats (*Otomys auratus*) and forest shrews (*Myosorex*).

If we believe the models (backed up by historical data), the western Soutpansberg will no longer provide suitable habitat for Sourveld small mammals by 2050, making it really important to secure strongholds in the eastern Soutpansberg, like Entabeni, which is the only site to still retain *Otomys auratus* records.

Roads and traffic are destructive to animal populations in many ways; by fragmenting habitats, genetic isolation of populations, and changes in land-use, and through mortality from wildlife-vehicle-collisions (WVC; *i.e.* roadkill), which has an immediate impact (Collinson et al 2015, 2019)

Collinson *et al.* (2014, 2015, 2017, 2019) have undertaken four studies in the VBR to determine the impacts of roads on biodiversity, specifically the Greater Mapungubwe Transfrontier Conservation Area (Figure 38) since it is expected that recent coal mining and tourism developments will result in elevated traffic volumes.

The upgrading of the freight rail infrastructure is key to the objective of shifting more freight from the road network to the rail network as well as finding the balance between road and rail in respect of the transportation of goods. Plans to upgrade the railway line and the surrounding substations in the VBR have been proposed.

Figure 38: Left to right: Undertaking roadkill surveys in the VBR. Photos: Wendy Collinson

3.3 Biodiversity involved in provision of ecosystems services

The biodiversity of the VBR is described in detail in the nomination application of the VBR and will not be repeated here. It is also summarised in point 2.2 and aspects related to revised conservation planning are outlined in point 4. An updated species list is annexed to this Review.

3.4 Updated ecosystem services assessment during the past ten years.

The Conservation Service Division of South African National Parks (SANParks) conducted a habitat assessment for ecosystem services in the VBR in 2014. The results indicated that 72% of the surveyed habitats were of high enough quality to provide the necessary services.

In 2014, an assessment was conducted by Univen's Research Chair on the water quality and ecological status of selected rivers in the VBR using diatom-based indices.

A decline in water quality was observed specifically in urban regions such as Thohoyandou. This decline, due to anthropogenic impacts, has led to eco-degradation which includes a decline in species diversity.

These results provide baseline information to the VBR for engagement with different authorities to assist in remedying the current challenges regarding threatened ecosystems.

4 CONSERVATION

4.1 Significant changes in main habitat types, ecosystems and species

There have been no significant negative changes in the VBR regarding habitat types, ecosystems and species over the past ten years and no species are known to have become extinct or are in immediate danger of becoming extinct.

4.2 Main conservation programmes

1. The provincial Department of Environmental Affairs (LEDET) produced a Conservation Plan (C-Plan) for the Limpopo Province. This plan identifies, so called, Critical Biodiversity Areas (CBA's) based on biodiversity hotspots, and the occurrence of rare species and threats. Two categories are identified based on irreplaceability namely CBA1 and CBA2. The CBA areas form the basis for biodiversity planning in the VBR.
2. A significant factor has been the establishment of the Chair on Biodiversity Value and Change in the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve at UNIVEN. The Chair acted as an important hub for biodiversity assessment and through its students, provided valuable information on various topics related to biodiversity conservation planning.
3. The Endangered Wildlife Trust joined the conservation efforts of the VBR by purchasing land for conservation, establishing an administrative centre in the western Soutpansberg area of the VBR, initiating a stewardship programme and running a predator conflict resolution programme. They are also running an extensive invasive exotic plant eradication programme in the Soutpansberg.
4. LEDET appointed consultants to draw up management plans for all the provincial nature reserves that make up the existing core areas.
5. There are various research centres in, and older than the VBR. These centres provide valuable information for conservation planning and make an extremely valuable contribution to the development of much needed local expertise of especially younger people.
6. In August 2011, a workshop (comprising conservation experts), was held to identify biodiversity hotspots in the VBR based on species diversity and the occurrence of red data species. The workshop found that the Limpopo River Valley, Pafuri area, the whole Soutpansberg and the Blouberg-Makgabeng are biodiversity hotspots. The workshop also identified ecosystem fragmentation due to human population growth and agricultural expansion, alien species invasion and mining, as the main drivers of biodiversity loss.
7. In 2012, the Conservation Task Team participated in several months of intensive discussions with consultants appointed by the mining company Coal of Africa (CoAL), to try and find a solution to the threats of mining. Unfortunately, this ended in a deadlock, but it helped to develop local expertise in handling these matters.

In addition to the above outlined targets, further studies have been undertaken in the VBR that provide further information of the status of biodiversity. These are outlined below:

- **Water Quality and Ecological Status Assessment**

A [Water Quality and Ecological Status Assessment](#) of selected rivers in the VBR was conducted in 2014 for a period of six months to include both high and low flow scenarios. The project was initiated by the South African Research Chair Initiatives together with the University of Limpopo. Diatom-based indices, fish biodiversity and the health status of the fish were determined.

The main goal of this project was to better understand anthropogenic impacts on water quality, nutrient status and biodiversity.

- **National Spatial Biodiversity Assessment (NSBA)**

The [National Spatial Biodiversity Assessment](#) (NSBA) is a product of high scientific importance led by SANBI in collaboration with DEFF and several other partner organisations.

The purpose of the NBA is to assess the state of South Africa's biodiversity based on best available science, with a view to understanding trends over time and informing policy and decision-making across a range of sectors.

The NBA is central to fulfilling SANBI's mandate to monitor and report regularly on the status of the country's biodiversity, in terms of the National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act (NEMBA, Act 10 of 2004). The NBA links closely with the National Biodiversity Monitoring Framework, which establishes a set of core biodiversity indicators for the country.

The South African National Spatial Biodiversity Assessment (NSBA) has included the Blouberg and Soutpansberg complex as one of its nine priority areas.

- **Kids in Parks programme as part of the ['Working for/on Programmes'](#)**

The [Kids in Parks Programme](#) is an initiative of DEFF together with SANParks and Pick n Pay retailer.

The programme was established in 2005 and it provides a unique opportunity for learners and their educators to visit national parks and learn about South Africa's natural and cultural heritage. During 2015, 42 learners in the Mutele area joined such a trip in the KNP.

This programme plays a pivotal role in providing meaningful environmental learning, within the framework of outcome-based education and the National Curriculum Statement, to equip future leaders with the knowledge, skills and values required to act for the environment. Mapungubwe National Park (a World Heritage Site) and Kruger National Park which form part of the core area in the VBR, host the Kids in the Parks Programme.

Figure 39: Left: Maribou Stork. Right: white rhinoceros (Mapungubwe National Park). Photos: Wendy Collinson.

- **Aichi Targets**

All Biosphere reserves in South Africa are recognised under the National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan for 2015 to 2025, as one of the programmes which assist in the implementation of the Convention on Biological Diversity's (CBD) Strategic Plan for 2011 to 2020.

The VBR contributes to the implementation of this Strategic Plan, particularly on Aichi Targets as discussed here below (Table 10):

Table 10: The contribution by the VBR to implementation of the National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan for 2015-2025, as well as the Aichi Targets

Aichi Target #	Target	VBR Contribution
1	People are aware of the values of biodiversity and the steps they can take to conserve and use it sustainably.	The VBR is involved in educating the public primarily through the Schoemansdal Centre for Environment Education (24 km west of Louis Trichardt). School groups and the general public are educated about the environment and the importance of ecosystem services such as, clean water and air. The Centre also organises field trips and hikes for primary and high school learners.
2	Biodiversity values have been integrated into national and local development and poverty reduction strategies and planning processes, and are being incorporated into national accounting, as appropriate, and reporting systems.	The VBR plays a pivotal role in regional landscape planning in line with the Spatial Planning and Land Use Management Act (SPLUMA - Act 16 of 2013), and therefore has a critical part in the implementation of the Integrated Development Plans (IDPs) of the relevant municipalities.
7	Areas under agriculture, aquaculture and forestry are managed sustainably, ensuring conservation of biodiversity.	<p>The VBR works with the agricultural sector by assisting with the Land-Care project growing indigenous trees and plants for the alien-clearing and river-restoration projects.</p> <p>The VBR also assists with the monitoring of alien-clearing projects by monitoring the cleared areas via drone-taken photos.</p> <p>The VBR has a project through LEDET officials, where we assist schools with growing their own vegetable gardens. The biosphere reserve helps with the set-up, if needed, and supply of vegetable seeds and seedlings for these school gardens. It is then up to the school to keep the garden going with the biosphere reserve doing follow-ups.</p>
9	Invasive alien species and pathways are identified and prioritised, priority species are controlled or eradicated, and measures are in place to manage pathways to prevent their introduction and establishment.	The VBR partners with LEDET and DEFF for an alien clearing project in the VBR. Alien vegetation, from river systems in the VBR, and replacing these with indigenous species. The Nombhela Community Indigenous Tree Nursery, located in Bungeni village, propagates trees for reintroduction into areas where biodiversity has been destroyed.
11	At least 17 percent of terrestrial and inland water, and 10 percent of coastal and marine areas, especially areas of importance for biodiversity and ecosystem services, are conserved through effectively and equitably managed, ecologically representative and well-connected systems.	The Biodiversity Conservation Strategy of the VBR proposes that core conservation areas be expanded to reach the targets set out in the National Environmental Management Protected Areas Act (NEM: PAA - Act 57 of 2003).
14	Ecosystems that provide essential services, including services related to water, and	The VBR is involved in several water projects and initiatives such as Adopt a River Programme in

	contribute to health, livelihoods and wellbeing, are restored and safeguarded, considering the needs of women, indigenous and local communities, and the poor and vulnerable.	partnership with the Department of Water and Sanitation. This programme is targeting women in the local communities to assist with cleaning the river systems.
18	The traditional knowledge, innovations and practices of indigenous and local communities relevant for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity, and their customary use of biological resources, are respected, subject to national legislation and relevant international obligations, and fully integrated and reflected in the implementation of the Convention with the full and effective participation of indigenous and local communities, at all relevant levels.	<p>The VBR Sustainable Living Centre has a medicinal area run and managed by local herbalists. They not only teach visitors about the various medicinal plants but also about the importance of conserving these plants through sustainable harvesting and the problems arising from illegal poaching and overharvesting.</p> <p>The VBR facilitates ongoing discussions with traditional healers and herbalists with regards to the protection of medicinal plants. The aim of these discussions is to set up medicinal plant gardens for herbalists to harvest material from, rather than to destroy wild flora with unsustainable harvesting.</p>

4.3 Conservation activities linked to sustainable development

The VBR through their task teams involves various stakeholders responsible for specific disciplines. This provides for an integrated and inclusive platform to cater and balance all these disciplines.

The VBR serves as a catalyst for coordinated management efforts of the landscape insisting on a balance between conservation management and sustainable development. An extensive [Stewardship Programme](#) has been proposed and initiated in certain areas to expand the core conservation areas on private and communal land. (Appendix H)

A summary is given below, of how the conservation of biodiversity in the VBR was enhanced in the following ways over the past ten years:

- 1) The compilation of a meta-database on sources of different aspects of biodiversity in the VBR, administered by the Chair in Biodiversity Value and Change at UNIVEN;
- 2) The compilation of a revised biodiversity conservation plan, including a rezoning proposal compiled by the Conservation Task Team with the help of a team of experts. (Appendix C);
- 3) Gazetting of all provincial nature reserves that were not legally conserved when the nomination application was prepared;
- 4) Compilation of a database on all other legally conserved land such as private nature reserves and forestry conservation areas

- 5) Extensive ongoing engagement with mining companies to ensure that the impact of mining on biodiversity is mitigated;
- 6) The Conservation Task Team engaged with SANParks to ensure that their buffer zones that fall within the VBR, are integrated with the newly proposed biodiversity conservation strategy;
- 7) The Chair in Biodiversity Value and Change compiled a database on bat roosts;
- 8) Dr Sarah Venter of EcoProducts is recording, measuring and monitoring populations of Baobab trees in the VBR to determine trends in survival;
- 9) The VBR is supporting an extensive research programme by Durham University in England, on conflict mitigation between farmers and large predators or primates in the VBR. This included the appointment of a community outreach officer;
- 10) An extensive public participation process with private landowners and community leaders throughout the VBR to secure additional private land legally conserved through the Stewardship Programme. This led to the creation of the Luvhondo Nature Reserve in the Western Soutpansberg. Additionally, several farms in the Soutpansberg and vicinity are now in the process of being legally conserved, some through cooperation with the EWT;

4.4 Assessment of the efficiency of actions

The VBR is now entering an implementation phase that will require extensive public participation. A detailed Management Plan will be required to coordinate the work and should build upon the strategic guidelines of the initial SEMP already done. This work will require paid personnel and therefore, a suitable budget to implement this last phase of the Management Plan.

The effectiveness of VBR is monitored, quarterly, by LEDET, a provincial department in South Africa. Furthermore, government agencies responsible for conserving natural resources such as, SANBI and tertiary institutions, regularly assess and monitor the quality of water and biodiversity.

The government of South Africa through DEFF and other government agencies, evaluate and assess management of protected areas across South Africa using the Management Effectiveness Tracking Tool for South Africa (METT-SA), which was adapted to meet the standards of South Africa. LEDET applies the METT-SA regularly on their reserves which forms the primary core areas of the VBR. The VBR core areas are therefore also subjected to their assessment and evaluation.

4.5 Main factors influencing conservation efforts

The main factors influencing conservation efforts are summarised below:

- 1) Fortunately a large part of the biodiversity hotspots of the VBR are situated within the Kruger National Park, in traditional extensive game farming or tourist areas in the Limpopo River Valley or in parts of the mountainous Blouberg and Soutpansberg, that are unsuitable for farming and other developments, therefore these areas are not under widespread immediate threat.
- 2) The rapidly growing human population, coupled with high unemployment and poverty presents a serious threat however, and in many parts of the VBR, residential areas and subsistence farming is impacting pristine areas. Fortunately, many local communities have embraced the biosphere concept and it should be possible to alleviate these threats by better urban planning and sustainable projects to create jobs.
- 3) The scarcity of water and competition with water requirements for mining is limiting the expansion of irrigated crop farming. Some farmers ignore legislation and if the laws are not enforced it may have serious negative impacts, particularly in sensitive mountain catchment areas.
- 4) Mining is a potential threat, not only for the environment in the long term, but also for human well-being. If mining replaces other sectors, such as agriculture (which is the main employment sector in the VBR currently), the immediate loss of many (relatively unskilled) jobs, is imminent. In the longer term, when mines are no longer operational (for example, Tshikondeni Mine at Makuya in the VBR, which closed once it had exhausted its minerals), a strain is placed on the job market-situation. Furthermore, rehabilitation of land is often at great cost before suitable (if ever) food-production and other purposes can then be applied.
- 5) Climate change with concomitant droughts and flash floods, probably presents the greatest threat to both biodiversity conservation and the quality of life.
- 6) The proposed development (for example, mining) in the VBR, will entail upgrades to existing transportation networks, such as rail and road. Road and rail are already recognised as a threat to multiple species, and the likelihood of increased negative impacts is severe (Figure 41).
- 7) Involvement of local communities and local authorities also influence the success of conservation in the VBR. To this end the VBR has made it a priority to involve local communities, environmental and developmental non-profit organisations as well as traditional leadership structures in the area.

Figure 40: Left: Ground Hornbill Right: Flap-neck Chameleon (both species are vulnerable to being roadkill). Photo Wendy Collinson

5 DEVELOPMENT

5.1 Trends in the main economic sectors of the VBR

5.1.1 BACKGROUND

Approximately 97% of the VBR's population reside in rural areas. The VBR has a sizeable population, in excess of 1 500 000, most of whom are relatively poor and live in local villages, with very few economic opportunities. The primary economic generators in the VBR are agriculture and mining, with agriculture by far the biggest employer. Tourism is a relatively small economic generator.

The tertiary sector is undoubtedly the biggest economic contributor, largely represented by the urban centres, such as Thohoyandou within the VBR, although the major proportion of the population reside in rural areas and most do not directly benefit from the economic benefits produced by the tertiary sector.

Considering the above, one of the biggest challenges facing the VBR is to produce and execute a long-term management plan to demonstrate how the VBR can contribute towards sustainable development.

According to the Integrated Development Plans for the Vhembe and Capricorn District municipalities, commercial agricultural farming forms 25% of land use in the VBR, commercial forest use about 7%, grazing land is 35% and towns are 2%.

A summary of the main economic sectors within the VBR has been extracted from the Department of Rural Development and Land Reform's (DRDLR) policy report: *District Rural Development Plan Vhembe District Municipality Limpopo Province; March 2016*, (Appendix I).

5.1.2 TRENDS IN AGRICULTURE

There is a declining trend in the agricultural sector demonstrated by a reduction from 29% of the district Gross Value Add (GVA) in 1995 to 24% of the district GVA in 2013. Notwithstanding this decline, the DRDLR states that it *"must put emphasis on agriculture as the cornerstone of rural economic transformation."*

The DRDLR states that their District Rural Development Plan for the area will act as the catalyst for transformational medium and long-term change in order to create resilient rural economies based on sustainable development principles, using what the Department refers to as "Green Growth". There is however, little indication of how this is to be achieved.

The DRDP forms part of a range of strategic spatial planning instruments as well as other sector plans aimed at transforming the apartheid space economy. In achieving the goal of economic inclusivity and transformation, agricultural development has been identified as one of the critical sectors that can unlock development.

The appreciation of agricultural development in the VBR should be located within an appreciation of the country's agrarian transformation agenda. In other words, the development of an inclusive and competitive agricultural sector is informed by the appreciation of on-going land reform processes as well as land tenure systems that continue to evolve."

From the above statement, it is clear that the government's policy is to encourage the growth of agriculture and transforming the apartheid space economy. However, this, even according to the DRDLR, is going to be challenging for the following reasons:

- 1) Most of the land used for farming results in constant environmental threats.
- 2) Most of the land is owned by traditional authorities or is privately owned and that affects land availability.
- 3) Due to the issue of land claims, there is no ability or little incentive to develop land. The town planning scheme focuses on the urban areas of the local municipality and neglects the rural areas.
- 4) Land invasion and illegal demarcation of sites in proclaimed areas by traditional authorities pose a constant challenge.

- 5) Most of the land which falls under traditional authorities hinders development. There is no land for development in and around urban centres like Sibasa and Thohoyandou.
- 6) Like most rural districts, the VDM is faced with severe service delivery challenges as well as a lack of physical infrastructure.
- 7) Whilst land claims in the area threaten to destabilise development, the uncertainty of land ownership especially regarding state owned land and tribal owned land, hinders development and future investments.

The DRDLF summarises the challenges by stating that *“rural areas are faced with the triple challenges of poverty, unemployment and a lack of service delivery.”*

5.1.3 TRENDS IN MINING

Mining within the VBR presents opportunities for economic growth and employment but often results in long-term negative implications on the environment (if not rehabilitated carefully).

Of greater concern, is proposed mining in the VBR’s future Buffer Zones as well as adjoining future Core Areas. This is aggravated in the case of proposed large-scale open cast coal mining. Areas where there are mining operations in the VBR include:

- Copper in the Musina field;
- Tshipise Magnesite field;
- Mudimeli Coal Fields;
- Tshipise, Pafuri and Mopani coal fields;
- Beit bridge Complex (Limpopo belt, which is host to minerals ranging from iron, diamonds, graphite, marble, talc deposits, gemstone deposits clay and other dominant minerals used in brick making);
- Blouberg-Makgabeng platinum group minerals;
- Sand mining (often illegal) of various river systems.

The plan below depicts the extensive areas within the VBR having mineral deposits and where prospecting is taking place. Prospecting has happened in the Madimbo corridor, area Mutele in 2018.

Of major concern are the extensive potential coal deposits adjoining the Mapungubwe World Heritage Site as well as the area adjoining and to the north of the biodiverse Soutpansberg shown in black on the plan (Figure 41).

Figure 41: A map showing extensive areas within the VBR having mineral deposits and where prospecting is taking place

However, the VBR is now in a stronger position to contribute towards guiding future land-use development, including mining, with the Conservation Task Team having completed its environmental sensitivity analysis of the entire area.

The VBR Conservation Task Team has also produced a revised plan indicating the environmental sensitivity of the area by proposing new as well as extensions to the Core Areas and Buffer Zones.

5.1.4 TRENDS IN TOURISM

The VBR is relatively remote and lesser known in comparison with the traditional and more popular tourism areas such as the Western Cape, Kruger National Park, the Drakensberg and the Midlands area in KwaZulu-Natal. However, the VBR attracts many tourists to our internationally-acclaimed tourism destinations, such as, Mapungubwe National Park - World Heritage Site and the northern Kruger National Park (especially the biodiversity hotspots of the Pafuri area north of the Levubu River where the Makuleke

community's concession lodges operate on the community's restituted land). The VBR also links the Great Limpopo and Greater Mapungubwe Transfrontier Conservation Areas.

Our region's rich cultural heritage has been relatively well-preserved as a result of its historic isolation. However, our underdeveloped infrastructure still restricts access to most parts of the VBR with pockets of untouched land reachable only by 4x4 vehicles – this creates opportunities of visits to specific audiences.

Since 2009, there has been an increase in international tourists to the area, with preferences that combine a nature and big game experience with real and 'non-contrived' cultural, lifestyle village tours (which include, visiting authentic, traditional Venda and Tsonga homesteads, meeting 'real' people like the renowned Venda and Tsonga woodcarvers, traditional open-fire potters and traditional basket weavers and beaders in their normal, day-to-day environments).

This trend seems to coincide with a 'tech-detox-tendency' worldwide where people make an effort to spend quiet time in exclusive, unspoilt environments, which the VBR still has to offer in abundance. Coupled with this, the extraordinary biodiversity ranges from subtropical and mountainous to pristine bushveld including the rugged beauty of the Limpopo River Valley strung with ancient Baobab trees – making the VBR an extremely attractive destination.

The VBR has numerous cultural heritage sites. Some of these sites date back to early man which have left its imprint in over a thousand identified San Bushman rock art paintings in the VBR and historic places such as those found at Mapungubwe World Heritage Site. There are rock art and archaeological areas of interest in the Makgabeng area as well as in the Thulamela site towards the northern Kruger National Park. These sites present opportunities for the growth in tourism.

Other notable tourist attractions in the VBR include the Soutpansberg Birding Route which has approximately 38 bird watching sites and 540 different bird species. According to the DRDLR report (Appendix I), tourism facilities include approximately 142 accommodation establishments where 28% are graded 2-star, 23% are graded 3-stars, 13% are graded 4-star and 2% are graded 5-star establishments.

Several other annual activities attract special-interest groups, such as, the annual Kremetart 4-stage road cycle race and concomitant mountain cycle event⁵, the Land of Legends Marathon, Two- countries Marathon (Botswana and South Africa), and the 4x4 challenges in Thate Vondo and Tshipise. Within the

⁵ <http://kremetartcycling.co.za/>

VBR three countries (namely Botswana, Zimbabwe and South Africa) combine to organise the annual Tour de Tuli mountain bike challenge. This event is in the Greater Mapungubwe Transfrontier Conservation Area (formerly the Limpopo-Shashe Transfrontier Park) and has the potential to grow in attracting tourists to the VBR.

Other tourism areas that have the potential to develop, especially for local tourists, include Dongola Transnational Park, the Soutpansberg, Nwanedi Nature Reserve, Baobab Nature Reserve, northern Kruger National Park, Langjan Nature Reserve, Happy Rest Nature Reserve, Dzata, Lake Fundudzi, Thate Vondo Forest and Phiphidi Waterfall (Figure 42).

Figure 42: Local artisans that can be supported by tourism. Left: At the Cultural Heritage Centre at Madi a Thavha Middle: Japhter Luvhimbi, one of the VBR's talented young woodcarvers Right: Making a traditional grass mat in a Tsonga Village.

According to the DRDLR report, the following key natural resources can be expanded and developed into future tourism attractions: Nwanedi Conservancy, western Soutpansberg, Lake Fundudzi, Matshakatini, Nandoni Dam, the Breathing Stone on Tswime Mountain, Komatiland Forest, Mutale Gorge, Mukumbani Waterfall, Tshatshingo Potholes, Mandadzi Waterfall, Big Tree (Baobab), Dongodzivha Dam, Tshavhadinda Cave, Tshipise Sagole Spa and Aventura at Tshipise.

The proposed new gate into Kruger Park at Shangoni, is located in the Thulamela Local Municipality and part of the VBR yet the main access road would be via Giyani that falls under Greater Giyani Local Municipality just outside of the VBR. This location would provide access to activities in the VBR (Figure 43).

Figure 43: Less contrived and real day-to-day life of rural people can be experienced in the VBR, traditional music instruments, traditional food as the Mopani worms on the photo in the middle above.

5.2 The state of Tourism and the influence of the VBR

As outlined above, the VBR has yet to develop its resources to directly influence the tourism industry; this will form the next phase of operations for the VBR. There exists a number of groups that support research-tourism, such as: Mogalakwena Research Centre and Lajuma Research Centre.

5.3 Other key sectors and its effects

There has been little change in the agricultural sector - which is the dominant land use in the VBR – during the review period. The section above outlined the challenges facing agriculture.

5.3.1 STEWARDSHIP PROGRAMME

One of the main initiatives arising from the work undertaken within the VBR is located in the western Soutpansberg. The EWT, an internationally recognised non-profit company, have acquired a few properties in the western Soutpansberg with the aim of contributing towards the protection of this sensitive and bio-diverse environment. They are in the process of developing a Stewardship Programme along the length and upper reaches of the western Soutpansberg. This proposal has received the support of LEDET.

The EWT describe the Stewardship Programme as follows:

“Within the suite of types of biodiversity stewardship agreements, the two higher levels, nature reserves and protected environments, allow for the establishment of protected areas on private land. These protected areas are recognised as such by the state, formally declared by the national Minister of Environmental Affairs and provincial MEC for Environmental Affairs in terms of the National Environmental Management: Protected Areas Act (Act 57 of 2003) (hereafter referred to as the Protected Areas Act), and are as secure as state-owned protected areas. By allowing for protected areas to be declared on private land, the state is not required to carry the cost of purchasing and managing the land, although tax incentives to support landowners do effectively shift a portion of the cost onto the state. Biodiversity stewardship is recognised in the National Protected Area Expansion Strategy as a key mechanism for achieving national protected area targets.”

This programme will not only assist in the long-term conservation of the area but will act as a catalyst for tourism and potential benefits to local communities in the area.

5.4 Benefits of economic activities for local communities

The three existing main urban centres, that is, Makhado, Thohoyandou and Musina, are the main economic contributors and, notwithstanding the opportunities available in these towns, there is still a very high percentage of unemployment. To date, the VBR itself has not been able to offer any direct concrete economic benefits to local communities. What it has been able to achieve is to establish a vision of how the region, and especially rural areas, can be exploited in a sustainable manner.

The work of the VBR Board over the last 10 years has been based on the following principles, as set out in the South African Biosphere Manual wherein it is stated that Biospheres can:

- Contribute towards the integration of the natural environment with the cultural assets of the people to jointly promote the sustainable utilisation of the area;
- Empower local communities to take responsibility for the development & conservation functions of the areas in which they live;
- Contribute towards creating partnerships between local communities, private sector and Government (CPPP) in order to share knowledge and co-operate in the use of its natural resources; and,
- Contribute towards the restitution process by acting as an innovative tool for the resolution of land use conflicts.

Based on the above principles the VBR Board indirectly contributed by developing partnerships and collaborations as well as promoting current demonstration models.

With greater financial support, sustainable development would be capable of contributing towards benefitting local communities in its future work programmes.

5.5 Assessment of efficiency of actions

Since its inception 10 years ago, the VBR has focused its work on analysing the opportunities and constraints presented by the diverse environment while considering its population distribution. The VBR consists of a large area, being in excess of 200 km by 120 km, with limited resources to progress further than it has to date.

The VBR has however contributed a lot in terms of the research that it has done in the area and some of this research has really changed some communities' lives. Also the awareness that we have carried out in the biosphere in partnership with other stakeholders has also gone a long way in educating the communities of the importance of the Man and Biosphere Programme. Some of our demonstration projects have assisted communities in taking action towards taking care of their environment and others have managed to generate a source of income from the projects.

5.6 Community economic development initiatives.

The VBR is committed to assist in local community upliftment through the promotion and recognition of Biosphere Demonstration Projects (BDP) in the VBR.

The VBR has provided a vision and guidelines (See appendix M Guidelines and data base for VBR Biosphere Demonstration Projects) as to how the VBR can contribute towards the socio-economic upliftment of local communities and believes it will make a significant difference in demonstrating the potential benefits of the VBR to the large number of predominantly rural communities this way.

The VBR has produced a set of criteria and guidelines in 2017 (Appendix M) that will form the basis of a proposed *"VBR Manual for establishing and promoting Biosphere Demonstration Projects"*.

Included will be a proposal to establish a skills training programme for future Biosphere Field Training Officers, with the aim being to create a set of sustainable livelihoods and development skills for local communities.

BDP's are aimed at supporting projects that fulfill the three core functions of Biospheres that is:

- 1) Conservation;
- 2) Development; and,
- 3) Logistics (which includes, education and research).

These will be projects that conserve the ecological and cultural value of a region, while simultaneously promoting sustainable development. These BDP's will also create awareness through research and education of the importance of the region from both its ecology and its cultural heritage and how the environment can be utilised for socio-economic development. The objective is to establish, give recognition and promote existing BDPs in the VBR to act as models that can be replicated elsewhere. The following are the guidelines for a project to be classified as a BDP in the VBR;

- 1) The natural environment can be utilised for commercial benefit, subject to this being undertaken in a sustainable manner;
- 2) BDP's must result in a benefit to local stakeholders;

- 3) It must make sustainable use of the environment and should have minimal, if any, negative affect thereupon;
- 4) It must result in long-term benefits to local stakeholders and the promotion of sustainable livelihoods; and,
- 5) It must follow the “Triple P Principle” that is, in making “Profits”, one must consider “People” and the “Planet”.

Any project comprising the following will be capable of being classified as a Biosphere Demonstration Project:

- 1) Research relating to the conservation and sustainable use of flora and fauna;
- 2) Research into the conservation and promotion of cultural heritage;
- 3) Innovative use of indigenous knowledge systems and appropriate technology which result in promoting sustainable livelihoods, including the following;

Traditional medicines and health, Local aromatic plants, Arts and crafts, Indigenous food systems, Building technology, Music, Promotion of eco and cultural tourism, Promotion of health and improved nutrition, Promotion of permaculture and organic farming, Promotion of agro-processing in a sustainable manner, and Education and skills training in the field of promoting sustainable development.

The following are a few examples of existing Biosphere Demonstration Projects recognised by the VBR:

5.6.1 BIOSPHERE DEMONSTRATION PROJECTS IN THE VBR

EcoProducts baobab seed oil & powder project⁶

EcoProducts purchases Baobab fruit from rural communities. The fruit is processed in their factory in Makhado to extract Baobab powder and Baobab oil. The extracts are packaged and sold to retail stores, in bulk to local and international manufacturers of food and cosmetic products. Since 2005, income generated has brought economic benefits to the lives of over 1200 women in the VBR (Figure 44).

The EcoProducts Foundation allows benefits to flow directly to the care for the ancient Baobab trees and to the lives of the people, predominantly, women and children, who live around them. (Figure 45).

⁶ <https://www.ecoproducts.co.za/>

Figure 44: Baobab guardians in traditional Venda attire with Dr Sarah Venter, owner of EcoProducts

EcoProducts

- Is a local business in the VBR that extracts Baobab fruits' healing oil from the pips and nutritious powder from its fruit.
- Is Certified Organic and sustainable, supports the Green Economy in South Africa and demonstrates high quality and standards.
- Supports over 800 rural harvesters, of whom 98% are women who live in areas of Vhembe with a very high unemployment rate.
- Employs 50 people in the processing of baobab fruit.
- Runs a Baobab guardian program and created the Baobab Foundation to make a strong connection between global markets and the locally sourced baobab fruit. The Baobab Foundation support several pre-schools in the rural communities where fruit are harvested.

www.ecoproducts.co.za

Figure

45: Promotional material for EcoProducts

Further examples of BDPS in the VBR include:

- Madi a Thavha Mountain Lodge⁷ (Figure 46; a social development and enterprise scheme);
- H12 Leshiba⁸ (Figure 47; a wildlife reserve and ecolodge);

⁷ <http://madiathavha.com/>

⁸ <https://www.h12leshiba.co.za/>

- Dzomo la Mupo⁹ (Figure 48; with a focus on empowering women and propagating indigenous plants and trees, developing homebased nurseries for knowledge to be transferred to family and children);
- Green Farms (Figure 49; commercial farmers using natural pest control in the Levubu Valley in some Macadamia orchards ; and,
- A proposed establishment of the Vhembe Centre for Sustainable Development and Education.

Madi a Thavha mountain lodge

- Offers business opportunities, training and marketing for 40 plus rural artisans in Vhembe and employs 20 people at the lodge.
- Meet high tourism standards: Fair Trade certified in Tourism since 2008, four-star graded, TripAdvisor certificate of excellence for 4 consecutive years.
- Madi a Thavha mountain lodge received a silver award from the World Travel Market in World Responsible Tourism Awards of 2018, the biggest responsible tourism event globally.
- Our holistic approach entails: lodge facilities, cultural activities and tours, a sewing workshop and a Cultural Heritage training centre at the lodge and a Limpopo CraftArt Centre at Victoria Yards in Johannesburg.
- We support local artisans by visiting them with guests, selling, training workshops and marketing. Our business model is based on mutual benefits.

www.madiathavha.com

Madi a Thavha
mountain lodge

Figure 46: Promotional material for Madi a Thavha Mountain Lodge

⁹ Dzomo la Mupo

H12 Leshiba

- Venda Village internationally renowned as an exceptional example of the rich cultural heritage of the Venda people and artists.
- Lodge and Indigenous Knowledge centre built the traditional Venda way, enhanced with appropriate technology.
- Off the Eskom grid. Use solar for lighting, water heating and boreholes.
- Guests get their vegetables and herbs fresh from our organic permaculture garden.
- Fair Trade certified.
- Non-profit programmes run by Leshiba Trust at the Luvhondo Centre of Indigenous Knowledge, part of an holistic approach to do sustainable and responsible tourism in harmony with our natural environment.

www.h12leshiba.co.za

Figure 47: Promotional material for H12 Leshiba

Dzomo La Mupo

- Dzomo La Mupo has a strong focus on empowering women and propagating indigenous plants and trees, by developing homebased nurseries for knowledge to be transferred to family and children.
- In 2018, DLM grew 12 000 indigenous trees , which were planted at local schools, at the traditional blessing-ceremony of the Cultural Heritage Centre at Madi a Thavha mountain lodge, Thohoyandou Botanical Garden and around the traditional councils' buildings of Thulamela, Makhado and Mutale municipalities in the VBR.
- Fosters inter-generational learning experiences between elders and youth to revive indigenous knowledge of the environment and its protection.
- In 2019, DLM will collaborate with the SARChI Chair at the University of Venda to support tree planting activities in the villages outside the Tshidzivhe-Thathe Vondo and Entabeni Forestry Reserves and to develop a book of Vhavenda indigenous plants and traditional management practice for schools.

www.dzomolamupo.org

Figure 48: Promotional material for Dzomo La Mupo

Natural pest control saves macadamia farmers millions

- South Africa is the world's leading macadamia producer and the Levhuvhu River valley in the VBR is a major growing region. Production is set to double in five years. Sustainable practices are vital to avoid widespread habitat losses and potential biodiversity losses due to insecticides
- Insect pests like stinkbugs cause economic losses to the South African industry of USD 6,823,827 (2017). Monkey damage of premature nuts causes estimated losses of USD 5,251,648 annually.
- Ongoing experiments involving researchers from University of Venda and University of Göttingen lasting three years excluded bats and/or birds from macadamia trees to estimate their economic impact on pest insects. Removal of birds and bats cost farmers an estimated USD 5 million per ha (60% of the expected yield based on control trees). This benefit hugely outweighed the costs of raiding by monkeys (USD 1.5 million).
- Natural habitat edges bordering macadamia orchards provided far greater economic services than non-natural edges, emphasizing the critical importance of conserving natural vegetation.
- Future studies in the next four years will extrapolate these results over broader geographic scales to understand the impacts of climate change. With the input from commercial and small-holder growers, researchers will investigate different economic scenarios. Many local farmers, major national macadamia nut processors, the Subtropical Fruit Growers Association and Macadamia SA are all supporting this ongoing research programme

Figure 49: Promotional material for Green Farms

Figure 50: Left Giraffe at H12 Leshiba Middle. Functional art, the hooks of woodcarver David Murathi. Right: Pink coral tree flower quite scarce in the VBR.

Figure 51: Indigenous lily of Soutpansberg Middle Venda clay pots of Nzhelele Right Mojaji cycad in VBR

6. LOGISTICS

6.1 Main institutions of research and monitoring in the VBR

6.1.1 UNIVERSITY OF VENDA (UNIVEN)

The VBR has partnered and signed an MoU with UNIVEN. UNIVEN hosts the South African Research Chair in Biodiversity and Change in the VBR, a vibrant hub for biodiversity science, training and conservation application in the Southern African Development Community (a body of established and emerging researchers, postgraduate and postdoctoral candidates).

The Research Chair, co-hosted by the Centre for Invasion Biology at the University of Stellenbosch, is funded by the Department of Science and Technology (DST) and administered by the National Research Foundation. (NRF).

Some of the main scientists conducting research and monitoring in the VBR (including those active in the last ten years but not currently active) are listed below with their areas of specialisation and institutions. Although not a comprehensive list, it gives a clear indication of organisations involved and areas of research (Table 11).

UNIVEN, located in Thohoyandou, is one of few universities in the world within the borders of a biosphere reserve. Several departments and schools at UNIVEN undertake both natural and social and health science research that has direct relevance to sustainable rural development and conservation in the VBR.

These include the Departments of Botany, Zoology and Microbiology in the School of Mathematical and Natural Sciences, the Departments of Ecology and Resource Management, Hydrology, Mining and Environmental Engineering, Geography & GIS and Urban and Regional Planning in the School of the Environmental Sciences, The Departments of Advanced Nursing and Public Health in the School of Health Sciences, the Department of Early Childhood Development in the School of Education, and the Institute for Rural Development and Departments of Animal Science, Soil Science and Food Science and Technology in the School of Agriculture.

Some of this research is mentioned in the list of researchers below, but this is by no means complete.

After its first five-year term, the Research Chair at UNIVEN, was renewed by the NRF for another five years in 2018 (2019-2023) and is eligible for another five years of funding after this.

In its first six years, the Chair trained 20 Honours, 20 MSc and 10 PhD students and five postdoctoral fellowships and published over 60 scientific publications (Appendix J) in four main fields:

- 1) Biodiversity conservation;
- 2) Ecosystem services and livelihoods;
- 3) Invasion biology
- 4) Global Change

Table 11: The main scientists conducting research and monitoring in the VBR (including those active in last ten years but not currently active)

Name	Research	Organisation
Professor Irene Barnhoorn	Fish health, water quality	UNIVEN/Zoo
Professor Pascal Bessong	Infectious diseases, medicinal plants	UNIVEN/Mic
Wendy Collinson	Road ecology	EWT
Dr Natasha Constant	Forest restoration, indigenous knowledge, human-wildlife conflict	UNIVEN/SAR
Farai Dondofema	Remote sensing of vegetation cover and alien invasive trees in the VBR	UNIVEN/Geo
Vince Egan	Herpetology, conservation planning	LEDET
Professor Derek Engelbrecht	Birds	University of
Professor Stefan Foord	Spiders, entomology	UNIVEN/Zoo
Professor Paul Fouché	Fish ecology, river health	UNIVEN/Zoo
Professor Joseph Francis	Rural community development; local economic development; water and sanitation; food and nutrition security	UNIVEN/Inst
Dr Marizvikuru Mwale	Ethnoveterinary medicine, water security	UNIVEN/ Inst
Professor Ian Gaigher	Fish, general biodiversity, conservation planning	Lajuma Rese
Professor Wilson Gitari	Environmental pollution, mining	UNIVEN/Eco
Dr Norbert Hahn	Botanist mainly Phytogeography and taxonomy, conservation planning, Herbarium Soutpansbergensis	UNIVEN (Adj
Dr Ali Halajian	Wildlife and fish parasites and diseases	University of
Dr Russell Hill	Primates and predators in Soutpansberg	Durham Uni
Ryan Huyssteen	Herpetology, conservation	Lajuma Rese
Professor Afam Jideani	Food technology	UNIVEN/Foo
Dr Elsje Joubert	Pest insects in subtropical fruits	UNIVEN/SAR
Edmore Kori	Climate and soils in the VBR	UNIVEN/Geo
Professor Lunic Base Khoza	Public health, nursing	UNIVEN/Adv
Professor Antoaneta Letsoalo	Conservation planning, ecosystem services of protected areas	LEDET
Maanda Ligavha-Mbelengwa	Traditional use of local plants	UNIVEN/Bot
Bibi Linden	Samango monkeys, primates	UNIVEN/Laju
Jabu Linden	Herpetology, conservation planning	Lajuma Rese
Dr Valerie Linden	Bats, agro-ecology	UNIVEN/SAR
Dr Khathutshelo Magwede	Traditional use of local plants	UNIVEN/Zoo

Tonderai Makoni	Heritage sites, cultural ecosystem, services, traditional knowledge and conservation in VBR	UNIVEN/SAR
Dr Caswell Munyai	Ant ecology and taxonomy	UKZN (forme
Professor Jude Odhiambo	Soil and crop science, climate change	UNIVEN/Agr
Professor John Odiyo	Hydrology, environmental pollution	UNIVEN/Hyd
Professor Jason Ogola	Environmental pollution from mining and waste	UNIVEN/Mir
Prof Natasha Potgieter	Water microbiology, virology	UNIVEN/Mic
Professor Amidou Samie	Infectious diseases, medicinal plants	UNIVEN/Mic
Dr Colin Schoeman	Entomology, especially beetles of VBR	UNIVEN/Zoo
Dr Karen Steenkamp	Conservation planning, protected areas	LEDET
Dr Lourens Swanepoel	Carnivores, rodents, ecosystem services and disservices	UNIVEN/Zoo
Professor Peter Taylor	Mammalogy especially bat and rodent taxonomy, ecology and ecosystem services	UNIVEN/SAR
Professor Saafi Traore	Water quality, public health	UNIVEN/Mic
Professor Peter Tshisikhawe	Indigenous knowledge of local plants	UNIVEN/Bot
Professor Ben Van der Waal	Fish ecology	UNIVEN/Zoo
Dr Sam Williams,	Predators, human-wildlife conflict	UNIVEN Zoo
Dr Sina Weier	Bats, ecosystem services in macadamias	UNIVEN SAR
Dr Katy Williams	Predators, human-wildlife conflict	UNIVEN/Zoo

Figure 52: Mapungubwe Hill World Heritage site and home of the ancient Golden Rhino

The current incumbent of the Chair, Professor Peter Taylor, also serves as Convener of the Research and Education sub-committee of the VBR Board and Committee. The Chair also established the Vhembe Biosphere-UNIVEN Museum and Resource Centre based at the School of Mathematical and Natural Sciences at UNIVEN. This contains natural history exhibitions, reference and teaching collections, books and library resources, offices, a GIS server and postgraduate student laboratory. The centre is used for undergraduate and postgraduate teaching and research and for seminars and workshops. All this had a positive impact on the quality of education at UNIVEN and the quality and quantity of research undertaken in the VBR.

6.1.2 MARA RESEARCH STATION

Mara Research Station, under the Department of Agriculture and Rural Development, conducts agricultural-related research on animal husbandry.

6.1.3 MADZIVHANDILA AGRICULTURAL COLLEGE

Madzivhandila Agricultural College undertakes research on crop production and fish breeding.

6.1.4 LAJUMA RESEARCH CENTRE (HOSTING THE PRIMATE PREDATOR PROJECT, DURHAM UNIVERSITY, UK)

By hosting international and local researchers and students, this centre has facilitated considerable biodiversity research and monitoring based in the western Soutpansberg through links to numerous local and international universities, predominantly in the Luvhondo Private Nature Reserve, but also throughout the VBR. Approximately 70 scientific publications (Appendix J) conducted at or including Lajuma Research Centre (LRC) cover a wide range of topics including primates, small mammals, spiders, insects, predators and human-wildlife conflict. LRC also provides training in biodiversity sampling and environmental issues/monitoring to local and international university groups and has established a fund for the inclusion of local students from Limpopo universities in the research programmes. Several weather stations have been maintained on the site for several years including one managed by the South African Environmental Observation Network.

A notable long-term study is a transect of insect pitfall traps over an elevational range on both southern and northern aspects of the Soutpansberg which has been conducted annually for eight years under Stefan Foord at UNIVEN (Zoology Department) resulting in several publications.

6.1.5 ENDANGERED WILDLIFE TRUST

Different projects of the EWT have had a focus in Limpopo and particularly in the VBR. For example, the Wildlife and Transport Programme of the EWT has been active in a comprehensive review of road killed

vertebrates in the vicinity of Mapungubwe National Park (Collinson et al. 2015). Other projects initiated by the EWT in the VBR include:

- Water conservation and alien plant removal in the Soutpansberg;
- Biodiversity stewardship;
- The use of livestock-guardian dogs to reduce human-wildlife conflict;
- African wild dog metapopulation; and,
- Carnivore census surveys.

6.1.6 LIMPOPO DEPARTMENT OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT, ENVIRONMENT & TOURISM (LEDET)

Desmet *et al.* (2014) produced the second version of the Limpopo Conservation Plan, providing a map of critical biodiversity areas for the entire province, including the VBR. This map was based on a variety of biodiversity features from various sources, including *inter alia*, threatened plant and bird species, additional reptile areas (LEDET), cheetah and wild dog records (EWT), wetlands, important bird areas, Freshwater Ecosystem Priority Areas catchments (FEPA), and vegetation types.

6.1.7 SANPARKS

SANParks have a Scientific Services division, under which regular research is conducted, which feeds into conservation planning. SANParks is also the institution responsible for the management of two core zones of the VBR; the Kruger National Park and Mapungubwe National Park. The VBR cooperated with SANParks on the integration of their buffer zones with the VBR's proposed zonation plan and continues to provide input on the Greater Kruger Strategic Development Programme.

Figure 53: Aloes in the winter grass on the slopes of Lajuma summit of the Soutpansberg

6.1.8 OTHER

Other institutions facilitating research in the VBR are the Kutetsha Research Camp and the Mogalakwena Research Centre. Kutetsha is being managed by Dr Sina Weier (previously facilitating research at the Goro Nature Reserve on the northern slopes of the Soutpansberg).

Most research at the Kutetsha Research Camp is conducted in cooperation with the Lajuma Research Centre.

Joint on-going projects are the distribution of Cape Clawless Otter (*Aonyx capensis*), use of marking trees by large mammals and research on the habituation of Samango monkeys (*Cercopithecus erythrarchus schwarzi*). Dr Sina Weier is working as a Postdoctoral Fellow under Professor Peter Taylor (UNIVEN), with a research focus on bats (*Chiroptera*).

She is currently also co-supervising an on-going project on seed dispersal of fruit bats in the VBR, conducted by PhD student Vusani Mphethe (UNIVEN) as well as an MSc project by Antonia Hammer (University of Bochum), comparing insectivorous bat diversity between the Luvhondo Private Nature Reserve and the Levubu farming landscape (both in localities in the VBR).

6.2 Main themes of research and monitoring

As mentioned under section 6.1, UNIVEN, Lajuma Research Centre, LEDET, EWT and other institutions have conducted research within the biosphere reserve in the past ten years, covering, inter alia, the following thematic areas:

- Biodiversity, ecology and conservation
- Ecosystem services and livelihoods
- Invasion biology
- Global change
- Human-wildlife conflicts
- Indigenous knowledge systems (IKS)
- Agriculture
- Public health and infectious diseases

Table 12 below summarises biodiversity-related research conducted and published under some of these above themes, primarily under the Research Chair on Biodiversity Value and Change in the VBR, UNIVEN and the Lajuma Research Centre.

In some cases, biodiversity conservation layers , for example, distribution of Red-listed and endemic species and sensitive roosts of bats and Vultures were incorporated into the interim SEMP which assisted in the development of both the Vhembe Bioregional Plan (LEDET 2017) as well as newly proposed core and buffer areas for the VBR.

In other cases, collections or sightings were deposited into museums and public data repositories such as the Avian Demography Unit's (ADU) Bird Atlas, Reptile Atlas and Virtual Museums, iSpot, iNaturalist, the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and published checklists, thus contributing to the national bioinformatics objectives of SANBI.

Figure 54: Images of various invertebrates detected in the VBR. Photos: Wendy Collinson

Table 12 : Details of research undertaken in the VBR

Abbreviations: Durham University (DU), Endangered Wildlife Trust (EWT), Green Dogs Conservation (GDC), Herbarium Soutpansbergensis (HS), Lajuma Research Centre (LRC), Panthera (P), Rhodes University (RU), Soutpansberg Centre for Biodiversity and Conservation (SCBC), University of Colorado (UC), University of Greenwich (UGr), University of Göttingen (UG), University of Illinois (UI), University of Kwa-Zulu Natal (UKZN), University of Limpopo (UL), University of Pretoria (UP), University of Venda (UNIVEN).

Projects/ activities	Geographical focus	Stakeholders/ beneficiaries	Resources/ funding	Key
Samango ecology, behaviour, distribution and conservation threats	Luvhondo NR, Soutpansberg, Levubu	VBR, EWT	DU/LRC	J.S.
Ecology and distribution of other primates and predators	Luvhondo NR, Soutpansberg	VBR	DU/UC/LRC	P. F.
Small mammal ecology, distribution and conservation	Luvhondo NR, Goro NR, Soutpansberg, Vuwani	VBR, SANBI	UNIVEN/UI/UP	M.A.
Bat taxonomy, distribution and conservation	Soutpansberg, Blouberg, Limpopo Valley, Levubu, rural villages in east (e.g. Vuwani)	SANBI, VBR-SEMP	UNIVEN	V. L.
Bird distribution, especially Red-listed birds and Vultures	Throughout VBR	ADU (Bird Atlas), VBR-SEMP	UNIVEN/UL/LRC	D. E.
Reptile and amphibian distribution and conservation	Soutpansberg, Vhembe district	SANBI, VBR-SEMP	LRC/SCBC	W.F.
Spider & scorpion taxonomy, distribution and conservation	Soutpansberg and for spiders, rural villages in east (e.g. Vuwani)	SANBI, ARC, VRB-SEMP	ARC/UNIVEN/SCBC	A. D.
Insect taxonomy, distribution and conservation; especially butterflies, ants and beetles	Soutpansberg, Limpopo Valley and rural villages in east (e.g. Vuwani)	SANBI	UKZN/UNIVEN	S.H.
Red-listed and endemic plants	Soutpansberg, Blouberg	VBR-SEMP	HS/UNIVEN	N. H.
Mapping and mitigation of road-kills	Mapungubwe Kruger NP	SANParks, VBR	EWT/RU	W.
2. Ecosystem services and livelihoods				
Biological control of insect pests by bats and birds in macadamia orchards	Levubu	Macadamia farmers	UG/UNIVEN	I. C.
Pollination ecosystem services of bees and other insects in macadamia and mango orchards	Levubu	Macadamia and mango farmers	UG/UNIVEN	S.H.
Biological control of rodent pests by mammalian and avian predators	Rural villages around Thohoyandou	Rural small-holder farmers	UNIVEN/UGr	S.W.
Mapping and control of alien invasive plants and establishment of forum	Throughout VBR	VBR, DAFF, DEAT, LEDET, Working for Water,	EWT/UNIVEN	

		SANParks, landowners		
4. Global change (climate change and land-use change)				
Impacts of land-use on invertebrate (ants, beetles, spiders) and vertebrate (birds, bats, small mammals, larger mammals) communities at two villages near Vuwani.		VBR, SANBI, ADU (Bird Atlas)	UNIVEN/UG	W.V.
Predicted impacts of climate change on montane rodents and shrews	Soutpansberg and other Afromontane areas	VBR, SANBI	UNIVEN	R.M.
5. Human-wildlife conflict				
Leopard and other predator distribution, habitat and human conflict, camera trapping, community engagement	W Soutpansberg, Alldays, Mara-Buysdorp	VBR, SANBI	DU/LRC/P/GDC	N.
6. Indigenous knowledge systems (IKS)				
Medicinal and other uses of local Vha Venda plants and cultural sites; habitat restoration	Areas of former Venda	VBR-SEMP, SAHRA	UNIVEN	N.

Figure 55: Typical view from slopes of the Western Soutpansbeg

Research on ecosystem services under the Chair has centred on predation and pollination services of biodiversity in Macadamia orchards on commercial farms in the Levubu Valley. South Africa is the world's largest producer of Macadamia nuts and much of this production comes from the subtropical Levubu valley in the eastern Soutpansberg area of the VBR. High-impact scientific and several popular articles have demonstrated the economic value of natural bird and bat pest insect predation services in macadamias (up to \$5000 ha/year).

The research also advocates retaining natural habitats in agricultural mosaic habitats to retain biodiversity-related ecosystem services. This ongoing research comprises a biosphere demonstration project for the value of integrated pest management in sustainable crop production.

Some of the key research outputs in the VBR include both peer-reviewed scientific and popular science articles. Over 100 scientific articles on the VBR were published in the last 10 years, see table above for details of research fields and a list of the publications and popular articles in Appendix J.

Figure 56: Left: San Rock Art on the Venetia Limpopo Nature Reserve. Middle and Right: Scenes from the VBR. Photos: Wendy Collinson.

6.3 Integration of local knowledge

The VBR has a number of projects that integrate local knowledge, some of which are outlined below:

- a) A private landowner has established a Centre for Indigenous Knowledge Systems at [H12 Leshiba](#) which coordinated various workshops and skills training on various aspects of indigenous knowledge systems over the past 18 years.
- b) In the Botany Department at UNIVEN, Professor Tshisikhawe (and students and colleagues) are researching indigenous plant species and their possible benefits to humans. In collaboration with the SARChI Research Chair, other projects have explored the ethnobotanical usage and role of traditional knowledge in conservation of rare cycads, as well as in relation to the disservices of

invasive plants such as the giant milkweed, *Calatropis procera* (completed PhD thesis of Siphon Mbambala in Botany Department).

- c) Working closely with a local community-based organisation, [Dzomo la Mupo](#) (DLM - meaning the Voice of Nature), an ongoing Chair PhD project (associated with the Chair), involves the assessment and mapping of cultural ecosystem services (particularly heritage sites) in the VBR. These are linked to community-based-study focus groups to understand the role of traditional knowledge and sacred sites in nature conservation and the zonation of the biosphere. The project will determine how to incorporate heritage data and IKS in conservation planning in the VBR. This will enable local communities to become more involved in conservation efforts and importantly, also assist them to protect the sacred sites which they value. Many conservation projects fail because they do not have the community support, so realising that sacred sites are important to most communities and that these sites are usually still pristine with a high number of indigenous species still present; it is crucial that VBR assist the communities to protect and register these sites.

- d) Also working closely with DLM, a project led by Chair Postdoctoral Fellow, Dr Natasha Constant, is using community engagement and mapping methods to foster forest rehabilitation in local Tshivenda-speaking communities. The research project aims to revive indigenous plant knowledge and traditional forest management practices alongside ecological research to support community management plans for the planting indigenous trees along riverine and degraded forest environments on community lands.

- e) Tree planting activities will be implemented by DLM. This project will also contribute to the development of a book of indigenous plants and traditional management practices for communities and schools.

DLM has a strong focus on empowering women and propagating indigenous plants and trees, developing homebased nurseries for knowledge to be transferred to family and children. DLM has grown 12 000 indigenous trees in 2018, which were planted at local schools, at the traditional blessing-ceremony of the Cultural Heritage Centre at Madi a Thavha Mountain Lodge, Thohoyandou Botanical Gardens and around the traditional councils' buildings of Thulamela, Makhado and Mutale municipalities in the VBR. In 2019, DLM will support tree planting activities in the villages of Tshidzivhe and Vuvha. The objectives of these indigenous tree nurseries are to :

- Plant indigenous trees and recuperate knowledge about indigenous plants in the VBR;
- Raise awareness about the VBR and the role of indigenous forests, rivers wetlands and fountains;

- Market the indigenous trees from Tshidzivhe-Thathe, Vhutanda and Vuvha home-based nurseries as a strategy to generate income for these rural communities;
 - Promote indigenous tree planting in schools, homesteads and communities' degraded areas, such as around the rivers, fountains and around wetlands areas; and,
 - Assist communities by reviving ecological care and knowledge to restore ecosystems in forests and wetlands, reviving ecological life in rivers and fountains by replanting the following plants; *Cyperus*, *Scirpus spaces*, *Colocasia esculenta* fern and moss plants.
- f) DLM also joined forces with other organisations of a similar focus in the local region. For example, collaborations have been formed with: Mudzi wa vhurereli ha Vhavenda, Vhangona Cultural Movement, Ndimba Community Services and the Vhembe Traditional Healers' Associations

Figure 57: Finger Millet ('Mufhoho' in Tshivenda) is sacred to the people of Venda and it is used for rituals (Mpambo) as well as for porridge/Vhuswa and the traditional drink Mabundu. DLM work with communities to revive this important crop, in order to conserve biodiversity and food security. Photo: Mphatheleni Makaulule

- g) An African-Union-sponsored project [on Ecologically-Based Rodent Management](#) (based at UNIVEN) is investigating traditional methods of rodent control and the importance of cats, dogs, wild carnivores and owls in biological control of rodents in rural villages near Thohoyandou.
- The same project is investigating the impacts of environmental education intervention in influencing community acceptance of owls and other native rodent predators.
- h) The social-enterprise development approach at Madi a Thavha Mountain Lodge, is to help preserve traditional skills embedded in IKS by 'up-cycling' functional traditional craft-items for modern applications.
- Madi a Thavha also facilitated the support of local artists, such as, Mischack Raphalalani to teach art in schools in the Makhado and Thulamela local municipalities.

6.4 Environmental and sustainability education.

We outline below examples within the VBR of environment and sustainable education delivered by various organisations.

UNIVERSITY OF VENDA

Apart from the formal training of undergraduate and postgraduate students in social, environmental and natural sciences at UNIVEN, the Vuwani Science Centre attached to UNIVEN, offers environmental education and curriculum enrichment programmes to school-children.

Between 2014 and 2019, the Research Chair on Biodiversity Value and Change in the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve offered eight ecology field schools, ten seminars and ten research skills workshops; this was mostly for postgraduate students from University of Venda. During this time the Chair supported about 20 Honours, 20 MSc and 10 PhD theses.

More than 40 Masters and almost 18 PhD students, who graduated from the Institute for Rural Development at UNIVEN, conducted their research in areas within the VBR (Table 13).

Bennde-Mutale 42 kids taken in to the Kruger as part of Kids in the Kruger 2014

Table 13: A summary of Research and Development Projects of the Institute for Rural Development at UNIVEN

#	Project	Focus	Funder	Collaborators
1.	Climate change & rainfall forecasting	Forecasting rainfall and temperature fluctuations via conventional and traditional methods; Livelihoods per household	Water Research Commission (2016-2018)	University of Cape Town's Climate Systems Analysis Group; South Africa Weather Services; University of Pretoria; UKZN; ARC; Limpopo Department of Agriculture and Rural Development (LDARD)
2.	Household Vulnerability	Estimating household vulnerability to food and water security; policy reform	IDRC through Financial and Fiscal Commission & Food Agriculture Natural Resources Policy Analysis Network (FANRPAN) 2013-2014	Thulamela Local Municipality (TLM); Mutale Local Municipality; Traditional Authorities; NGOs
3.	School Food Gardening	Development of a framework for strengthening food and nutrition gardening after opportunity and diagnostic survey of primary schools in the Sibasa Educational Circuit of Vhembe District	WesBank Foundation & UniVen RPC (2015-2016)	Department of Basic Education & other Government Departments; NGOs; Thulamela Local Municipality (TLM); JET
4.	Biosphere Demonstration Projects	Mentoring of three community-based projects dealing with environmental conservation, sanitation, income generation and aquaculture	Global Environmental Fund: GEF (2017 – Feb 2019)	Afristar; United Nations Office of Project Services (UNOPS); Limpopo Economic Development Environment & Tourism
5.	Water & Sanitation	In-depth survey of the state of water and sanitation in 178 villages in Vhembe leading to an all stakeholder community-organised symposium	UNIVEN (2017)	Adopt a River Forum; Department of Water & Sanitation; TLM & Collins Chabane Local Municipality; Vhembe Adopt a River Forum
6.	Water Security	Water studies seeking to develop solutions in partnership with multiple stakeholders	USAID (Partnerships for Enhanced Engagement in Research: PEER & NRF) (2017 – date)	Monash; UNISA; Montana University, USA
7.	Innovation for Local Economic	Innovation mapping and appropriate interventions for	Department of Science & Technology and Technology	VDM & 4 constituent LMs; Department of Cooperative Governance & Traditional

	Development	transformation of commodity value chains for improved incomes and job creation	Innovation Agency (2019-)	Affairs
8.	Amplifying Community Voices	Developing grassroots community resilience through facilitated inclusive decision-making platforms	WK Kellogg Foundation (2006-2010); National Research Foundation (2010-2012); UNIVEN	Traditional Authorities; Local Municipalities; Various community-based institutions and NGOs;
9.	Clean People's Minds to Trigger Sustainable Responsible Action	Monthly cleaning campaign involving multiple stakeholders; mobilising citizens to play a leading role in maintaining a clean physical, social and mental environment; and creating a facilitated public platform for lively deliberation and inclusive decision making on the broad issues affecting local communities such as maintaining a clean environment, drug and alcohol abuse, service delivery bottlenecks, and deepening democracy, among others.	None	TLM; CCM; Murongwe Enrichment Projects; Vhembe Adopt a River Forum; many government departments; Traditional Authorities; NGOs; Amplifying Community Voices Students Association (ACVoSA)

ECOSCHOOLS run by WESSA (Wildlife and Environment Society of South Africa)

Eco-Schools runs an international programme of the Foundation for Environmental Education (FEE), developed to support environmental learning in classrooms. The programme aims to create awareness and action around social and environmental sustainability in schools and support Education for Sustainable Development in national curriculums. With over 50% of the content in all national curriculum subjects being environmental in nature, Eco-Schools makes a positive contribution towards improving education in South Africa.

There are currently 40 schools participating in this programme in the VBR. Teachers who participated in one of the Eco-School programmes, receive ongoing support with new teaching methods and resources such as the WESSA EnviroKids magazine. By partnering with higher education institutions, WESSA can deliver high quality materials endorsed by the Department of Basic Education.

Some of the following example-activities were completed at Eco-Schools in the VBR:

- Baseline audits were done to determine the state of the area of the school before projects are implemented;
- Action-learning projects related to findings of these audits were planned and implemented. Project themes were: Health and Wellbeing, Biodiversity and Nature, Community and Heritage, Water and Waste Management;
- Projects are linked to the national curriculum in Maths and Science subjects and the scientific method to implement projects are used. The projects further integrated learning into Technology, Social Sciences and Life Skills subjects; and,
- Monitored and evaluated action-projects were done for annual assessment through portfolios of evidence.

Some other examples are the Blouberg Eco-Schools in the VBR, who participated as citizen-scientists by submitting their waste audit results to a global clean-up campaign in partnership with the *Story of Stuff Project*. Volunteers around the world picked up litter during a set period and in addition to collecting waste, tallied what brands and products showed up most often. This data helps The Story of Stuff Project and its partners in the *#breakfreefromplastic* movement to identify the companies whose products most often end up in the environment, so we can work together to hold them accountable for their impact. The Blouberg Eco-Schools, Makgari and Mama Primary's, contribution was featured on this [international platform](#).

Eco-Schools are investigating their waste issues and finding ways to create value from it by making household products, which can also generate income. Learners have been exposed to the biodiversity around their schoolyard and learned about the value of pollinators in the production of crops. In light of climate change and the severe drought experienced in Blouberg, schools are saving and reusing every drop of water by using water-saving hand washing methods, using cups to drink water, reusing grey water to water trees and mulching the vegetable gardens to prevent evaporation. Learners are doing investigations on what plants need to grow to understand the growing of their own crops and are harvesting enough to supplement the feeding scheme and raise funds for their schools. Over 43 projects are implemented by 10 schools, which is transforming school environments and saving the schools money by using resources wisely.

SCHOEMANSDAL ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION CENTRE

The Centre teaches large school groups and the general public about the environment and the importance of ecosystem services such as clean water and air. The Centre also organises field trips and hikes for primary and high school learners.

OTHER

The Lajuma-based, Primate and Predator Project of Durham University conducts regular environmental education (school talks) and community engagement around human-wildlife conflict in the VBR region.

The VBR has identified that there is a need for a skills training centre where all aspects of sustainable development and sustainable livelihoods could be demonstrated. The existing Schoemansdal Environmental Education Centre was chosen as the ideal place to establish the proposed centre. Discussions were held with LEDET, which resulted in the Department preparing a report supporting the proposal and it is still on the agenda as a future project.

6.5 Efficiency of actions in Logistics

As described above, the SARChI Research Chair on Biodiversity Value and Change at UNIVEN has functioned as a champion for conservation, and sustainable development-related research in the VBR.

The Chair is evaluated every five years by an international scientific peer-review panel of the NRF based on performance. Based on its satisfactory performance in research and postgraduate capacity building from 2018-2018, the Chair was renewed by the NRF panel in July 2018 for another five years (2018-2022).

This means that it is fundable for another five years after that (that is, 2022-2026). The Chair works closely with existing staff members of UNIVEN to ensure the sustainability of the initiative.

Furthermore, the Resource Centre and the GIS Server established at UNIVEN will be maintained in perpetuity for the benefit of students and researchers and stakeholders.

In addition to UNIVEN environmental educational initiatives of WESSA and the EWT have been effective and are subject to assessment by their own respective NGO's.

6.6 Main internal and external communication mechanisms

The VBR's internal and external communication has been largely through email communication and social media. The AGMs are also used as a means of feedback sessions to the communities.

The VBR has a website www.vhembebiosphere.org and the [SARChI chair](#) at UniVen also has their own website. The VBR is active on Facebook, Twitter and Instagram and its handles are linked to the biosphere website. The VBR social network platforms are:

- Facebook: [Vhembebiosphere](#),
- Twitter: @Vhembebiosphere
- Instagram: @Vhembebiosphere

WhatsApp groups for Board members and the VBR sub-committees and task-teams works well in our rural South African conditions, since it is a quick, easy, traceable and cheap way to send messages, disseminate videos, photos, file attachments and GPS locations. Accessibility is a challenge in some areas and for some people, with poor cellular phone reception and relatively expensive data/Wi-Fi.

6.7 Contribution to the World Network of Biosphere Reserves

The VBR contributes to global biosphere reserves in the following ways:

1) Capacity building.

The VBR assisted in conducting Capacity Development sessions for UNESCO Global Communication Strategy to AfriMAB. Two VBR officials have been trained to conduct these capacity building training.

2) Collaboration with existing biosphere reserves at national, regional, and international levels.

The VBR has an exchange partnership with other South African Biosphere Reserves, through the Biosphere Reserve National Committee and the Limpopo Biosphere Reserve Forum. There is no international partnership with other countries, however there is an opportunity to establish a transboundary initiative with Zimbabwe and Botswana.

3) SPACES.

On an informal level, through the SPACES (Science Partnerships for Complex Earth Systems) consortium, collaboration between the SARChI Chair at UNIVEN, the Sustainability Institution at

University of Limpopo, the Global Change Institute at Wits University and three German universities is implementing research and Modeling projects to understand the impact of climate change on land use and land cover change in two biosphere reserves in Limpopo; the VBR and the K2CBR.

The SPACES projects (from 2013 - 2021) have provided recommendations to mitigate against drought and climate changes in VBR and K2C. In close association with communities, farmers and other stakeholders, ongoing projects will investigate various scenarios for different land uses under climate change, particularly in rural rangeland-maize and commercial macadamia systems.

4) Current and expected benefits of international cooperation

The VBR currently benefits from the international partnership that exists within the Transfrontier Conservation Areas (Greater Mapungubwe, and Greater Limpopo Transfrontier Conservation Areas). The VBR benefit in terms of learning-exchange and knowledge-transfer initiatives which are currently taking place particularly in the core areas of the VBR. Another benefit accrued in the Transfrontier Conservation partnership is increased tourism, through cross-border tourism products which include cycling and wild run.

5) Intended contributions to the World Network of Biosphere Reserve and to the Regional and Thematic Networks.

The VBR will continue to participate in information exchange programmes at MAB ICC and the African Network of Biosphere Reserves.

The knowledge generated from these projects should inform decision makers in Limpopo about possible alternative scenarios and sustainable land-use practices

7. GOVERNANCE, MANAGEMENT AND COORDINATION

7.1 Technical and logistical resources

The VBR has a coordination team comprising a Board of Directors, Coordinator and various thematic task teams including; Conservation, Development, Communication and Research and Education. In addition, the VBR is developing a Youth Forum, which will be facilitated by the Coordinator.

This 'team' has been on a voluntary basis with limited finances for reimbursement, which has always been a challenge for the effective administration of the VBR. This will change, with the direct funding from LEDET (instead of via the VDM) and the subsequent appointment of a VBR Coordinator from 1 July 2019.

Technical resources include the excellent and varied skills-sets of many of the Directors and conveners who volunteered their scientific, geographical, information technology, business and other skills over the past 10 years. On the other hand, a major challenge has been Board member attendance since the registration of the NPC, with a substantial minority of members failing to attend the obligatory three of four annual meetings. This created instances, especially during 2018, where no quorum was obtained for decision-making.

Other resources include those of the provincial government (LEDET) who have seconded a staff member to the VBR Board, as well as providing facilities for meetings.

UNIVEN also has active involvement of academic and research staff in the VBR, particularly pertaining to conservation planning and rural development. UNIVEN also provides further assistance through hosting workshops and assigning interns to assist with website maintenance and social media. DEFF have assisted with two workshops regarding the development of management plans and preparation of the periodic review.

7.2 Framework for Governance and contributions

From nomination in 2009 until 2013, the organisational structure of the VBR followed the framework outlined in Figure 58.

The VBR Non-Profit Company was registered in September 2013. Its constitution governs the execution of duties. The VBR NPC is primarily responsible for managing the VBR and its activities as seen in the diagram below.

Figure 58: VBR Stakeholder's Council structure (2009-2013)

Since 2009, the activities of the VBR were executed by a group of dedicated local volunteers, which operated under the direction of an elected representative Board-structure, comprising up to 12 board members, who were also volunteers. For the period May 2017-April 2018, a Biosphere Coordinator was employed part-time. There are five sub-committees to the VBR NPC namely: 1) Communications and Awareness; 2) Conservation; 3) Institution and Finance; 4) Research and Education; and, 5) Development, each with its own chairperson who reports directly to the VBR board of Directors (Figure 59).

Figure 59: The structure of the VBR NPC, as of May 2017

A challenge has been to ensure that VBR Board members that are elected, have the commitment to undertake work for the VBR, and further, who have the relevant experience, skills and means to attend the required number of meetings per year.

The VBR NPC works primarily in collaboration with the provincial LEDET through the MEC, who reports to the national DEFF who liaise with AfriMab and UNESCO (Figure 60).

Figure 60: The reporting structure of the VBR, as of May 2017

7.3 Social impact assessments to support local rights

There are no specific social impact assessments for the VBR, however South Africa is party to the Convention of Biological Diversity and has ratified the Nagoya Protocol.

All the programmes related to access and benefit sharing are regulated in accordance to the convention.

All social impact activities are aligned to the United National Convention on the rights of indigenous people. In addition, South Africa has developed national programmes which govern how local and indigenous communities should benefit from the natural resources, this programme is called the [People and Parks Foundation](#).

Figure 61: Hamasha gorge and H12 Leshiba and view from pool at their Venda village

7.4 Main conflicts and solutions implemented

The main conflicts regarding access to and use of resources.

Access to resources in the VBR are well regulated by legislation and enforcing governance and all new developments must be preceded by impact assessments. For this reason, conflicts are limited and usually confined to cases where the laws are ignored. Slow progress with land restitution and uncertainties related to this, have had a negative impact on investment and agricultural output in the region. However, generally new owners have been willing to participate in existing conservation projects when they obtain land in nature reserves through the restitution programme like the Makuleke community's well-known concession area in the land north of the Levubu River in the KNP and part of the VBR.

Two major conflicts or challenges occur within the area of the VBR; 1) Mining and industrial development; and, 2) land restitution.

1) Mining and industrial development

To date mining has had a limited impact in the VBR, but the resources are vast and extensive mining could pose a serious threat to tourism, biodiversity conservation and when completed, to employment.

There has been a large number of mining applications within the transitional and buffer zones since the proclamation of the VBR. These include plans for extensive open cast coal mining in the

Limpopo Valley and plans for mining of platinum group minerals in the Makgabeng-Blouberg area. Allied to the plans for coal mining, in 2016 the Minister of Trade and Industry gazetted the Musina Makhado Special Economic Zone (SEZ) within the area of proposed coal mining. The SEZ will see the establishment of an energy and metallurgical industrial park with a coal fired power station powering coking, ferrochrome, ferromanganese, ferrosilicon, pig iron metallurgy, lime, steel and stainless-steel plants. In attempts to resolve these conflicts the VBR has:

- Registered as an Interested and Affected Party on prospecting/mining applications, attended public participation meetings and sought expert input on commenting on environmental impact assessment reports and indicating where mining rights areas affect critical biodiversity or ecological support areas as per the Limpopo Conservation Plan and scientific opinion;
- Engaged directly with representatives of and consultants to mining companies in an ultimately unsuccessful attempt to establish a VBR mining forum of all stakeholders;
- Developed and distributed the VBR position paper on mining in 2013 (Appendix F) highlighting the International Council for Mining and Metals (ICMM) guidelines and distinguishing between the legal licence to operate and the social licence to operate. In particular the VBR noted the need for a cumulative impact assessment given the large number of individual mining applications, the need to protect water resources, competition for such resources with agriculture and the need to incorporate the land restitution process into development; and,
- Proceeded through the interim SEMP process, the work of the conservation task team and the promotion of mechanisms such as the stewardship programme to identify further areas to bring under conservation

2) Land restitution

The apartheid history of the area has resulted in a distorted land ownership. As a result, there are hundreds of land claims by local communities who were dispossessed of their original land. The new laws of the country enabled these people to legally reclaim their land. As a result, many local communities have successfully had their land restituted. The challenge however is that these communities do not have or are not provided with, the resources, skills or funding to develop their land sustainably.

The VBR can play an important part in this process through advocating the establishment of Biosphere Demonstration Projects and assisting to access skills and resources needed for sustainable development.

7.5 Representation and consultation of local communities.

All stakeholder-groups were invited to and were well-represented at the VBR's AGM. The biggest challenge for the VBR is to reach and consult with the approximately 1.5 million stakeholders of which the majority live in rural areas where the need for conservation and sustainable development is the greatest.

The AGM, where most representing stakeholder-groups are invited to participate, is open to all stakeholders and although well-attended, clearly it has limited potential to meaningfully engage with such large numbers with such different levels of education amongst stakeholders. Hence the VBR make is its mandate to engage with various stakeholders on a daily basis through various workshops and platforms. The current board of directors has members from the local university, research institution, representatives of community based organisations, youth representative, tourism operator and land owners.

How local people, including women and indigenous people are represented in the planning and management of the VBR

There is, unfortunately, limited representation of the local communities in direct management, purely for reasons of the scale of the challenge, as well as a lack of resources and funding. Through the SARChI chair at UNIVEN, however, various communities have been engaged through different platforms such as, the commercial Macadamia farmers in the Levubu Valley, and through Dzumo la Mupo Foundation (mostly joined and run by local women), as well as the work of the Institute for Local Development. For future projects it is essential that fully inclusive community participation takes place and promotes capacity building within the community

In any community organisation (either cooperative or non-governmental organisations), individuals have had equal opportunity to participate in the VBR and an open invitation exists for membership by any interested party. Companies or associations are invited to participate in the VBR task teams although participation has been low, since the nature of the voluntary role is unappealing to many. This may be exacerbated by the unemployment rate of 52% in the VBR, where the majority of people need to work, and can therefore not spare the time to support the VBR Board and, or task teams. Most people in the VBR need to work hard to make ends meet and to keep their precious jobs.

All recommendations proposed by the VBR are widely discussed (before they are submitted), with representatives from stakeholder groups including rural communities.

The VBR intends to link all the consultations undertaken in the VBR, to a decision-making mechanism.

This will enable the VBR to establish a long-term sustainable development plan for the conservation of the VBR for future generations.

Figure 62: Left: Dried pumpkin flowers, a rural delicatessen. Right: Tsonga woman at her traditional homestead, embroidering for a rural Craft enterprise as extra income

7.6 Management and coordination structures

7.6.1 CHANGES REGARDING ADMINISTRATION

There have been no fundamental changes to the administrative authorities of the VBR other than the amalgamation of Mutale Local Municipality and Musina Local Municipality and the establishment of the Collins Chabane Municipality as separate from Thulamela Local Municipality.

Core area management remains under the authority of SANParks and LEDET regarding national and provincial parks, respectively. Buffer and Transition zones remain under the authority of provincial, district and local government, government sector departments, landowners and traditional community structures.

There has only been a change in ownership of officially conserved land due to the creation of private nature reserves, such as the recently gazetted Luvhondo Nature Reserve. DEFF will also manage some core conservation areas if the recommendation for the inclusion of Forestry Reserves in the new core area is approved.

7.6.2 UPDATED INFORMATION ABOUT THE MANAGEMENT OF THE VBR SINCE 2009

As outlined above, the VBR is managed and coordinated by the autonomous VBR Non-Profit Organisation's Board of Directors. The VBR had coordinators to assist in the work of the Board during the past 10 years, but these have been on a voluntary basis by Board members who have had limited time at their disposal.

As the VBR covers an enormous area and has many challenges, it has not always been possible for the coordinator to meet the needs of the task at hand.

During the period of March 2017 to April 2018, the Board employed a part-time Coordinator who was responsible for day-to-day activities of the VBR.

The coordinator was assisted by the five task teams. Challenges with receiving the regular funding through the VDM led to a period (from mid-2018 to May 2019) with no coordination, although this has been resolved from July 2019 when the VBR has again employed a part-time coordinator (a person who has the experience, knowledge and the time to deal with this important position).

7.6.3 CHANGES IN MANAGEMENT STRUCTURE SINCE NOMINATION.

The changes, since proclamation of the VBR in 2009, involved the registration of a Non-Profit Company (NPC, registration 2013/050303/08) with the South African Companies and Intellectual Properties Commission in 2013 and the adoption of a guiding Constitution which stipulates the objectives, stakeholders, operations, management and governance of the NPC alongside the stipulations of the NPC Memorandum of Incorporation and the provisions of the Companies Act of 2008.

The Constitution is further guided by the Seville Strategy. Participants in the original nomination steering committee were eligible to stand as Directors and the Company was registered with nine initial Directors representing local organisations, eco-tourism initiatives, communities and academic institutions. Four office bearers included a Chairperson, Vice-Chairperson, Secretary and Treasurer. Directors are largely active in the coordination structure of the biosphere reserve and undertake this voluntarily.

The NPC was registered as a membership organisation and membership was formalised in the 2016 AGM to include individuals and individuals representing organisations and communities. No membership fee is levied, the only stipulation to joining is signing of a membership form endorsing the vision and mission of the biosphere reserve. Each member has one vote in the election of the Board, every three years.

A new Board of Directors was elected by the membership at the end of the 2020 AGM whose three-year term will be up for re-election at the 2022 AGM.

As a registered NPC the VBR is an autonomous entity as governed by the Board of Directors and the rights conferred to members as detailed in the Constitution of the NPC.

Notwithstanding this autonomy, the Board works closely with local and provincial governments who are represented at all meetings and with whom the VBR has signed a MoA in terms of funding received for specific projects and Board operations.

Furthermore, additional persons are seconded to act in roles of coordination and as conveners of the various task teams, reporting to the Board and attending meetings of the latter as well as reporting progress to members at the AGM.

7.6.4 HOW MANAGEMENT ADAPTED TO THE LOCAL SITUATION

Due to the financial and human resource constraints it has not been possible to meet many of the challenges facing the VBR. However, through registration of the autonomous entity (the NPC), the Directors' fiduciary duties are governed by the laws of the Republic of South Africa, as follows:

- 1) Through the adoption of a Constitution which lists representative stakeholder groups active in, or specific to the area of the biosphere reserve;
- 2) Through consultative management attempting to engage these stakeholders. Limited representation on multi-agency bodies such as the Vhembe District Land Development Forum and representation/collaboration with some local and national agencies and organisations through project phases;
- 3) Through registration as an Interested and Affected Party regarding developments and engagement with related public participation processes as governed by environmental legislation; and,
- 4) Through appreciation and recognition of national developmental challenges with regard to gaining adequate community representation.

7.6.5 ASSESSMENT OF EFFECTIVENESS OF MANAGEMENT

The challenges of VBR Board functionality (as outlined above), have created limitations in formally evaluating the effectiveness of management and coordination. However, the NPC was evaluated by the members at two full-day AGMs, as well as at the board elections (held every three years). Feedback was given on operations, progress and challenges to the membership.

The NPC is also evaluated by the company auditors annually, in terms of financial mechanisms developed and improved, unqualified audits of accounts since 2013 and provision of evidence (meeting minutes, registers, resolutions, policies) of the VBR NPC's functioning. Some evaluation of coordinator and conveners by the Board of Directors is in line with the coordinator scope of work and the mandate of the task teams.

Evaluation through quarterly reporting to the provincial government is in line with an agreed business plan. Annual narrative and financial reports have been sent to the provincial government since 2018.

Figure 63: Left: Giraffes of the Duluni valley in the Western Soutpansberg. Photo John Rosmarin. Right: Rock art at Khaoxa Shelter. Photo Wendy Collinson

7.7 Management policy update

7.7.1 MANAGEMENT PLANS AND THE ROLE OF THE AUTHORITIES IN IMPLEMENTATION

There have been no changes regarding the management policy and stakeholders involved.

An interim SEMP has been prepared as an interim management tool to guide conservation, development, research and skills training but an EMF has yet to be undertaken due to insufficient funds. DEFF initially offered to provide funds to undertake an EMF and Terms of Reference were developed between the VBR and DEFF; unfortunately, a national budget-cut to DEFF resulted in the renegeing of the offer.

7.7.2 THE PROGRESS REGARDING THE GUIDELINES OF THE MANAGEMENT POLICY

The *VBR Report to stakeholders 2009-2019* as outlined above has the following objectives:

- 1) To provide and convey the urgency of a strategic, holistic, long-term conservation and development plan based on the most recent scientific studies in the VBR and to show how it aligns with the national and international frameworks of which the VBR is a part;
- 2) To include a proposed future-expansion-plan of the Core Areas and Buffer Zones;
- 3) To demonstrate the potential of the VBR to contribute towards long-term sustainable development for our stakeholders;
- 4) To ‘workshop’ the report through an extensive public participation process; and,

- 5) To demonstrate how the VBR can contribute towards sustainable livelihoods through existing Biosphere Demonstration Models in various fields, such as tourism, production and processing of food and medicinal plants, and agriculture and social enterprise-services.

7.7.3 FACTORS ASSISTING OR IMPEDING IMPLEMENTATION OF MANAGEMENT POLICY

The VBR is such a huge landscape with so many stakeholders and conflicting land use patterns, so it is a huge challenge to reach all these stakeholders as often as we should.

A further limiting factor is that the major portion of the 1.5 million stakeholders reside in rural areas, so reaching out to them will require VBR to go and have meetings with all these stakeholders since most do not have access to the internet for social media.

However using the traditional authorities we have managed to make some headway into the communities

7.7.4 INTEGRATION OF THE VBR WITH NATIONAL STRATEGIES AND LOCAL MUNICIPAL PLANS

Integration of the VBR can be determined at the following provincial and local level plans which were developed since the 2009 proclamation:

- The VBR area and zonation were entered into the Marxan model for the development of the 2013 Limpopo Conservation Plan, which selected critical biodiversity and ecological support areas and produced land use guidelines for the categories.
- The VBR is therefore covered within the Limpopo Province Protected Area Expansion Strategy which developed from the Limpopo Conservation Plan.
- The VBR is included in the 2016 Limpopo Spatial Development Framework.
- The VBR provided input to and was included in the 2017 Vhembe District Bioregional Plan which also uses the Limpopo Conservation Plan as a basis.

From a conservation perspective, the regional strategies (through the work of LEDET), are well integrated with the work of the VBR and this has significantly contributed towards its achievements to date. This is less so regarding the local authorities where there has been minimal integration.

As previously mentioned, a major concern in integration is the processing of the many mining applications (and the proposed Special Economic Zones) within the VBR by the Department of Mineral Energy. There is the potential for long-term negative impacts on biodiversity by a number of these mining and heavy industrial projects, which will be located within or adjoining proposed new Core Areas and/or Buffer Zones.

Figure 64: Left: Master crafter Mishack Raphalalani's work. Middle: Master potters at Mukondeni's clay bowls. Right: Woodcarver David Murathi is well-known for his functional art.

8. CONCLUSION

Summary

Provided below is a summary highlighting the major changes and achievements made in the VBR since 2009. Justifications for the biosphere are based on Article 4 of the Statutory Framework of the World network of Biosphere Reserves.

1) We believe that our biosphere is justified as a site, with appropriate rationale (summarised below) for its zonation.

The VBR encompasses a mosaic of ecological systems, representative of major biogeographic regions, including a gradation of human interventions.

Based on the most recently published map of the vegetation types of South Africa the VBR includes three of the nine South African biomes namely; savanna, grassland and forest. Consequently, due to variation in climate and soil, the VBR is suitable for a variety of agricultural activities.

Game farming and the hunting industry have rapidly expanded over the past three decades, becoming one of the most important sources of revenue in the region.

Mining for diamonds, gold, copper, granite, coal and graphite take place at several sites in the proposed area.

Four relatively large urban areas are located within the VBR, namely Thohoyandou, Makhado, Musina and Senwabarwana. Numerous smaller villages are scattered throughout the traditional areas.

2) We believe our biospheres is of significance for biological diversity conservation

The VBR provides a viable model for the conservation of the three biomes and 25 unique ecosystem types in the VBR to enhance the quality of life of its inhabitants.

UNIVEN (and other research institutions) have developed extensive local expertise on biodiversity assessment and conservation, historical and archaeological resources, human development, economics and agriculture.

A vast data base on biodiversity has been accumulated since 2009, and this will enable local expertise to develop a biodiversity conservation strategy that will achieve targets set by the SANBI.

This will contribute significantly to national biodiversity conservation goals because of the remarkable biodiversity and high degree of endemism in the VBR.

3) We believe our biosphere provides opportunities to explore and demonstrate approaches to sustainable development on a regional scale

The VBR shares borders with Botswana, Zimbabwe and Mozambique and is therefore strategically situated to complement the following regional initiatives, currently receiving high priority:

- **Participation in the Transfrontier Conservation Areas (TFCA).**

The area of the VBR includes portions of two trans-frontier conservation areas, namely the Greater Mapungubwe TFCA and the Great Limpopo TFCA. The management of both TFCA's are guided by memorandum of agreement between the countries involved.

- **The Southern African Development Community (SADC)**

Currently SADC promotes strategies and measures aimed at harmonising economic policies, capacity building, gender equality and human resource development in the region. This is in keeping with the move towards an integrated African Economic Community (or AU).

4) We believe our biosphere is of an appropriate size to serve the three functions of biosphere reserves

Due to its relatively large size (30 700 km²) the VBR conserves a remarkable variety of 25 vegetation types and a large number of endemic or threatened plant and animal species. Furthermore, due to its wilderness character, as much as 18% of the surface area was already conserved in both the Kruger and Mapungubwe National Parks, and provincial nature reserves at its conception. The large size of the VBR enabled the inclusion of the entire Vhembe District Municipality and the Blouberg Local Municipality. This facilitates bioregional planning, including upliftment and human development in the proposed transitional zones.

The large area also enabled the inclusion of all transformed areas in transitional zones. Due to its size and variations in climate, geomorphology and soil, a variety of agricultural activities take place in the VBR.

Environmental awareness and maintenance of ecosystem services is essential for the sustainability of this industry.

Commercial agriculture with subtropical fruit, vegetables, citrus, cattle and game is well established and contributes significantly to the economy of the region. Tourism is a smaller but important role player, expected to grow in future.

The majority of the population is poor with limited resources and the biggest challenge in the region is to rectify the inequalities of the past.

The selection of the boundaries in such a way that whole municipalities are included has enhanced this process. The inclusion of five municipal regions, each of which forms a separate focal region for development, enhanced the scope for human development in the VBR. The VBR is a popular research area due to its interesting biological and cultural features. The establishment of the VBR provided a central platform for research and it became more coordinated and relevant to conservation and development during the past 10 years.

The size of the area is sufficient to test models of a multidisciplinary nature. Both the national and provincial government is dedicated to sustainable development and conservation in the region and the required programmes and infrastructure are already in place. Provincial government has a well-staffed environmental education unit and education programmes take place at several of the proposed core conservation areas. The National Parks Board runs educational programs in both the Kruger and Mapungubwe National Parks.

The provincial education department has been undertaking environmental education for many years at the Schoemansdal Environmental Education Centre in the Soutpansberg. NGO's, such as the Wildlife and Environmental Conservation Society of South Africa (WESSA) and the Endangered Wildlife Trust (EWT) also contribute to the environmental education efforts. UNIVEN's Research Chair on "Biodiversity Value and Change in the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve" (SARChI) proved to be the biggest game-changer in the VBR during the past 10 years.

Appropriate zonation to serve the three functions

The current zonation is still that of the nomination in 2009 as shown below in Figure 70.

Figure 65: Current zonation of the VBR

- 5) We believe that organisational arrangements should be provided for the involvement and participation of a suitable range of *inter alia* public authorities, local communities and private interests in the design and the carrying out of the functions of a biosphere reserve

After nomination in 2009, stakeholder groups appointed a Vhembe Biosphere Committee, which appointed a Project Coordinator whose responsibility was to coordinate five task teams, namely; 1) Conservation; 2) Development; 3) Research and education; 4) Communication and awareness; and, 5) Institution and finance.

In 2013, the VBR Non-Profit Company was established (according to the Companies Act of 2008). Its Board of directors managed the VBR from 2013 up until now. The Board is elected at the AGM and directors may serve for a three-year term. The Board of Directors has a Chairperson, Vice Chair, a Secretary, Treasurer and board members. The Board appoints the coordinator and chairs

of the five task teams. The Directors and task team members have all given their time voluntarily since 2009.

The VBR NPC reports to the Limpopo Department of Economic Development, Environment and Tourism (LEDET) who then reports to the Department of Environmental Affairs, Forestry and Fisheries (DEFF) who liaise with AfriMAB and UNESCO.

The following are mechanisms for organisation and implementation of activities in the VBR:

a) Mechanisms to manage human use and activities

The buffer zones consist of provincial nature reserves, privately owned game farms and communal areas. The provincial nature reserves have management plans to ensure that human activities do not impact negatively on the environment. These plans are implemented by experienced wildlife managers. Private landowners that own land in buffer zones are encouraged to form conservancies and the VBR NPC and task teams assist them to compile and implement management plans. The management plan of the biosphere reserve will formulate management strategies for buffer zones in communal areas.

b) Management policy or plan

Consultants will be appointed to compile a management plan for the proposed VBR based on the research already done for the Interim SEMP.

c) Authority or mechanism to implement this policy or plan

The management policies were implemented by the VBR Trust from 2009-2013 and from 2013-2019 by the VBR Non-Profit Company in both eras with the assistance and funding of the provincial Limpopo Department of Economic Development, Environment and Tourism.

d) Programmes for research, monitoring, education and training

The educational and research task teams have drawn up multiple programmes for research, monitoring, education and training. Most of this Research and Monitoring has been covered in the brief to SEF (Strategic Environmental Focus PTY Ltd), the consultants that drew up the interim VBR Strategic Environmental Management Plan, as a forerunner and work-in-progress document towards an EMF that the VBR NPC could not afford to do yet.

6) We believe our biosphere has cooperative activities with other biosphere reserves

At the national level:

The VBR is a member of the National Biosphere Reserve Committee and collaborates with other national conservation programmes in our biosphere, such as the World Heritage Sites, Transfrontier Conservation Areas (TFCA), Ramsar Sites and Stewardship Programmes.

At the regional level:

The VBR is interconnected and has linkages with the Kruger to Canyon Biosphere Reserve and Waterberg Biosphere Reserve through the Limpopo Biosphere Reserves Forum and with all South African biosphere reserves through the national committee.

Through twinning and/or transboundary biosphere reserves:

The VBR does not have a specific biosphere reserve twinning agreement, however it forms an integral part of the Greater Mapungubwe and Great Limpopo Transfrontier Conservation areas. Transboundary biosphere reserves with Zimbabwe, Mozambique and Botswana will be created as part of this initiative.

Within the World Network:

The Mapungubwe World Heritage Site is one of the Core Zones of the VBR. The VBR has participated in the World Heritage Site Management through representation at VBR meetings and engagement with DEA, with regard to the buffer zone modification.

The VBR falls within the Greater Mapungubwe and Great Limpopo Transfrontier Conservation Areas which are multi-lateral initiatives involving South Africa, Mozambique, Zimbabwe and Botswana.

The VBR participates in the World Network of Biosphere Reserves (WNBR) and the VBR has participated in and contributed to the African Network of Biosphere Reserves (AfriMAB) meetings and workshops and implements its recommendations where relevant.

Figure 66: Left ; Gold-plated sceptre of Mapungubwe. Right: Yellow-billed Stork

7) Obstacles encountered, measures to be taken and, if appropriate, assistance expected from the Secretariat:

Obstacles encountered

The main obstacle encountered during the Periodic Review period has largely been due to lack of a full-time administration to assist with the management of the VBR.

Furthermore, limited input from many Board members meant that additional workload was placed on other members.

Measures taken

A part-time Coordinator has been appointed which should assist in alleviating some of the challenges in Board functionality.

An external party was also employed to assist with overseeing the production of the Periodic Review.

Assistance from Secretariat

The Secretariat should continue to assist with the main objectives of the VBR.

Possible future assistance from the Secretariat could involve submission of changes to the zonation of the VBR given the current planning processes and the potential impact of extensive non-sustainable mining and industrial development within the VBR.

Main objectives of the Biosphere Reserve:

The VBR intend to fulfil its aim through the following:

1. Participate in the UNESCO MaB programme through relevant government agencies and structures.
2. Generate interest and active participation in environmental conservation amongst its members.
3. Conserve and enhance the natural environment including its indigenous fauna and flora, mountains and river systems, as well as its rich cultural heritage and historically important sites.
4. Promote the research and preservation of local indigenous knowledge systems (IKS) and with appropriate technology for the benefit of its stakeholders in the VBR.
5. Implement management strategies for the sustainable utilisation of the natural and cultural resources of the area.
6. Improve the quality of life of the people in the VBR through the creation of job opportunities through socio-economic upliftment, education, training, skills transfer and capacity building programmes.
7. Enhance the eco-tourism potential and tourism information network in the VBR.

8. Maintain a Biosphere Reserve Centre that will provide a local scientific and technical support service relating to all biosphere issues to all the stakeholders in the VBR.
9. Participate in joint ventures including but not limited to CPPP's (Community/Public/Private Partnerships) in order to promote the VBR on a local, regional and national scale.
10. Subject itself to National and Provincial legislation, policies relating to environmental, and IKS issues.
11. Conduct appropriate work in collaboration with existing institutions locally, provincially, nationally and internationally.
12. Coordinate all biosphere activities within the VBR according to the principles above and ensure that the activities of the VBR are transparent and conveyed to all stakeholders.

With the completion of the Initial SEMP (by the Conservation Task Team of the VBR), the following objectives have been identified as part of the next phase for the VBR, and intend to undertake the following:

1. Distribute to stakeholders the Executive Summary of the report on the VBR for the work undertaken to date;
2. Hold workshops on the above with a cross-section of key role player and stakeholder groups in order to explain the work to date and to specifically obtain comments on the proposed extension and expansion of the Core Areas and Buffer Zones;
3. Upon receiving the necessary Protected Area status, the VBR to approach LEDET, DEA and then UNESCO to update the current zonation plan;
4. The VBR to implement the proposals of the Development Committee in regard to the promotion of Biosphere Demonstration Projects;
5. The VBR to participate in commenting on all major new projects and specifically those related to the mining industry;
6. The VBR to actively promote the establishment of a skills training programme in sustainable development.

Figure 67: On top of the Soutpansberg

Figure : 68: Left: Landscape Western Soutpansberg. Right: At woodcarver Lucky Ntimani's rural gallery and garden

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Figure 69: From left to right: Traditionally fired and decorated V Venda clay bowl, traditional V Venda homesteads, intricately carved bowl of Ezerael Tavhana, typical dung floor patterns

Dedicated to Dr Ian Gaigher

Dr Ian Gaigher (26.10.1943 – 08.04.2020) was a scholar and conservationist with a passion for the Soutpansberg mountain range, the biodiversity hotspot and centre of endemism which forms the conservation core around which the concept of the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve was first developed. He was instrumental, during the early 1990's, in developing the first submission to UNESCO and served as the first Chair of the Conservation Task Team of the Biosphere Reserve, during which time he identified and lobbied for potential core areas to obtain conservation status in law. Through his mentorship and supervision of young conservation biologists at various universities, but particularly the University of Venda, where he was the Dean of Science from 1989 to 1994, he made a major contribution to both the theory and practice of conservation in Southern Africa. He established the Lajuma Ecological Research Centre in 1996, where he impacted the lives of young biologists undertaking internships at the Centre, from across the world. The Vhembe Biosphere Reserve is testament to his abiding legacy, and this submission is dedicated to him.